

COVARS

Comité de Veille et d'Anticipation des Risques Sanitaires
Committee for Monitoring and Anticipating Health Risks

Activity Report

2022-2024

COVARS

Comité de veille et d'anticipation des risques sanitaires

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The French Committee for Monitoring and Anticipating Health Risks (*Comité de Veille et d'Anticipation des Risques Sanitaires - COVARS*) is an independent and permanent scientific committee reporting to the Minister of Higher Education and Research and the Minister of Health and Prevention. It was created by decree on the 31st of July 2022 by the Prime Minister, succeeding the former Covid-19 scientific council (*Comité Covid-19*) and the Council on immunization strategy (*Conseil d'orientation de la stratégie vaccinale - COSV*), two committees created during the Covid-19 pandemic. COVARS' mission is to provide informed advice based on rigorous scientific data and to issue recommendations when a projection reveals a health risk, as well as to ensure scientific monitoring of health risks. Its prerogatives cover health risks linked to infectious agents affecting humans and animals, food, climate change, pollution and the environment.

Its members are appointed for a 2-year term, renewable once. The composition of COVARS is set by decree at 16 scientists and health professionals with expertise in health risks, and two representatives of health democracy. Chaired by Professor Brigitte AUTRAN, it is currently composed of 20 members, including an additional representative of health democracy and an expert in the human and social sciences. The diversity of its composition enable the committee to adopt a One Health approach of health risks.

Since it was set up on September 29, 2022, the Committee has been regularly consulted on infectious or environmental risks, and has taken up several key issues of health risk anticipation on its own initiative, to issue opinions, warnings and recommendations to the authorities in order to better prepare our country for the emergence or management of health crises.

This feedback and activity report summarizes COVARS' approach and working method and presents the main work and achievements of the first mandate ending August 2024. This report also aims to highlight COVARS' strengths, weaknesses and areas for improvement, particularly in its interactions with national and international institutions, and proposes future prospects and topics for the next mandate.

During this mandate, the Committee has helped strengthen the country's pandemic preparedness and issued various in-depth advices on emerging pathogens, epidemiological trends, best practices and societal issues in health preparedness and response, working with national and international institutions to ensure a coherent and effective approach to health risks. COVARS showed that it could play a leading role at the Health-Science-Society interface, complementing the work of health and research institutions by providing decision-makers with independent, rigorous and transparent analyses on health risk prevention and preparedness.

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I. COVARS' missions and composition

a. Missions as defined in the decree establishing COVARS

With the end of the provisions relating to the state of health emergency, the two independent advisory committees that were set up to manage the Covid-19 health crisis [the Covid-19 Scientific Council and the Council on immunization strategy (*Conseil d'orientation de la stratégie vaccinale - COSV*)] ceased their activities on July 31, 2022. To take over the tasks previously carried out by these two committees, the Committee for Monitoring and Anticipating Health Risks (*Comité de Veille et Anticipation des Risques Sanitaires - COVARS*) was created by **decree 2022-1099 on the 30th of July 2022**, instituted in article D. 1413-92 of the public health code (in appendix 1)¹, by the Prime Minister, Mme Elisabeth Borne, and placed under the dual supervision of the Minister for Health and Prevention and the Minister for Higher Education and Research (article 3 of the decree). Unlike previous committees, COVARS is a permanent committee and is not specifically linked to a state of health emergency.

The decree establishes its composition, operating procedures and missions, which are to:

- " -Ensure **scientific monitoring** of health risks linked to infectious agents affecting humans and animals, environmental and food pollutants, and climate change;
- Model the data collected as part of its scientific watch mission and draw up projections;
- Issue recommendations when a projection reveals a health risk;
- Issue recommendations on the measures planned by the public authorities to **combat a health crisis**;
- Issue recommendations, as necessary, on the vaccine strategy to be implemented, where appropriate, in response to a health threat identified by the committee

COVARS' advisory role therefore involves both anticipating risks and managing them. The mission statement of August 17th, 2022 (in appendix 3) indeed specifies that during crises, COVARS "*may become an advisory body to the Government*", and that outside crises, it "*works on the challenges of anticipating and preventing health crises and their consequences (scientific monitoring, prediction and modeling, recommendations to reduce risk and provide care and support to our fellow citizens)*". In addition to the ministerial referrals, COVARS can take on any issues falling within its expertise and scope. According to the decree, COVARS may "*for the exercise of its missions, pronounce on its own initiative or be referred to by one of the ministers with whom it is established*".

b. Composition of the Committee

The decree establishing COVARS specifies its membership, which is chaired by a qualified person appointed by the Ministers responsible for its establishment. "*It is also made up, on the proposal of its chairman, of : 1. sixteen leading scientists or health professionals; 2. a patient representative; 3. a citizen representative. In the event of a health crisis, the chairman of the committee may propose calling on additional personalities for their specific expertise. The chairman and members of the committee are appointed by decree of the ministers responsible for the committee, for a period of two years, renewable once.*"

¹ <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/jorf/id/JORFTEXT000046115261>

Prof. Brigitte Autran was appointed chairperson on August 16th, 2022, and subsequently proposed a list of members that fits the broad missions of the committee: experts in human health (epidemiologists, virologists, immunologists, modellers, infectiologists, general practitioners and emergency physicians, etc.), animal health (veterinarians, entomologists) and environmental health (environmental epidemiologists, ecologists), as well as specialists in the human and social sciences, and patient and citizen representatives. (see Appendix 2 for the order appointing COVARS members). **The multidisciplinary composition of COVARS reflects the scope of the committee's missions and affirms the interdependence of human and animal health and their ecosystems, by promoting a collaborative, transdisciplinary approach.**

Table 1: COVARS Composition

	Disciplines	Name	Status	Location	Institution	Research structure
Epidemiology	Infectious Diseases	Fabrice CARRAT	PU-PH	Paris	SU, Inserm, APHP	UMR 1136 Inserm/SU
	Health, Pollution & Climate	Rémi SLAMA	PU	Grenoble	Inserm, Collège de France	IRES, UMR 5309 UGA / Inserm U 1209 / CNRS
	Ecosystems, ecology, One Health	Patrick GIRAUDOUX	Professor Emeritus	Besançon	IUF, U. de Franche-Comté	UMR 6249 UFC/CNRS
	Modeling Infectious Diseases	Simon CAUCHEMEZ	DR	Paris	Inst. Pasteur	Institut Pasteur
Infectiology	Mal. Infect Hum.	Xavier LESCURE	PU-PH	Paris	UPC, APHP, Inserm	UMR 1137 Inserm/USPC
	Mal. Infect. Emerging, One Health	Denis MALVY	PU-PH	Bordeaux	CHU Bordeaux	UMR 897/1219 INSERM / U. Bordeaux
Medicine Support for 1st recourse	General Medicine	Olivier SAINT-LARY	PU	Paris	UPC	UMR 1018 INSERM/UVSQ
	Emergencies	Julie CONTENTI	MCU-PH	Nice/ West Indies	CHU Nice	
Virology	Respiratory and enteric viruses, One health	Bruno LINA	PU-PH	Lyon	CNR, HCL, Inserm	UMR Inserm U1111/ CNRS 5308, ENS Lyon, UCBL U. Lyon
	Arboviroses, Emergencies South, One Health	Xavier de LAMBALLERIE	PU-PH	Marseille	CNR, Inserm, APHP	UMR IRD 190, INSERM 1207 / EFS
Veterinary microbiology	One Health	Thierry LEFRANCOIS	DR	Paris/ Montpellier	CIRAD	Département Bios et UMR ASTRE CIRAD / INRAE
Entomology	Vector risks, One Health	Didier FONTENILLE	DR	Montpel-link	IRD	UMR CNRS / IRD / INRAE / U Montpellier
Vaccines	Vaccines and vaccine strategies	Brigitte AUTRAN	Professor Emeritus	Paris	Sorbonne-Université	UMR 1135 SU/Inserm/CNRS EA
	Innovative vaccines, One Health	Roger LE GRAND	DR	Fontenay	CEA	UMR1184 CEA / Inserm / U Paris-Saclay
Sciences Human & social	Sociology: Infections and Migrants	Annabel DESGREES from LOU	DR	Paris	IRD, CEPED	IRD, CEPED

	Health policies	Mélanie HEARD	Dr.	Paris	ScPo Paris	
	Social psychology and health crises	Jocelyn Raude (Associate member)	Pr	Rennes	EHESP	UMR ARENES UniR-CNRS 6051- Inserm 1309
Patients' Association Citizens' Representative Health Democracy	Health promotion/ Community health	Céline OFFERLE		Marseille	TRT-5 CHV	
	Vulnerable patients	Yvanie Caille		Paris	Renaloo	
	Action citoyenne et Aller Vers	Véronique LOYER		Paris	ANAMS	

Experts scientifiques

**Professeur émérite
Brigitte Autran
Immunologiste**

**Professeur
Fabrice Carrat
Epidémiologiste**

**Docteur
Simon Cauchemez
Epidémiologiste**

**Docteur
Julie Contenti
Urgentiste**

**Professeur
Xavier de Lamballerie
Virologue**

**Docteur
Annabel Desgrées
du Lou
Démographe**

**Docteur
Didier Fontenille
Entomologiste médical**

**Professeur émérite
Patrick Giraudoux
Ecoépidémiologiste**

**Docteur
Mélanie Heard
Politiste**

**Docteur
Thierry Lefrançois
Vétérinaire - One Health**

**Docteur
Roger Le Grand
Immunologiste**

**Professeur
Xavier Lescure
Infectiologue**

**Professeur
Bruno Lina
Virologue**

**Professeur
Denis Malvy
Infectiologue**

**Professeur
Olivier Saint-Lary
Médecin généraliste**

**Professeur
Remy Slama
Epidémiologiste
environnemental**

Représentants des usagers et citoyens

Yvanie Caillé
Représentante
de patients

Céline Offerlé
Représentante
de patients

Véronique Loyer
Représentante
des citoyens

II. Feedback and activity report

a- COVARS approaches to health risk monitoring and anticipation

The zoonotic origin of most emerging infectious risks, and the impact of the "Exposome" on ecosystems, underline the need to monitor and anticipate emerging health risks with a "One Health" approach. Indeed, infectious threats are closely linked to environmental changes, which favor the transmission and aggressiveness of pathogens. Furthermore, the international spread of these threats and exposures underscores the need for monitoring, anticipation and preparation on an international scale.

The Committee followed a collegial, scientific and inclusive approach, closely linking monitoring and anticipation, which can be broken down into several sequences:

- **Forward-looking scientific watch**
 - based on national and international health and environmental monitoring data and available scientific and bibliographical data on the various hazards, as well as expert **hearings** (around **130**) conducted by COVARS,
 - through relationships with health monitoring agencies, and through the professional networks of COVARS experts.
- **Anticipation** based on numerous expert hearings and scientific evidence

COVARS was invited to publish two articles on its unique approach and original contribution to anticipating health risks in two articles; a commentary in the journal *Nature Communication* and an Editorial in the journal *médecine-sciences*.² (see appendices 5 and 6).

b- COVARS' interactions with ministries and health and research institutions

According to COVARS' mission statement, "*The committee's work will be carried out in conjunction with existing research and innovation structures, as well as with the relevant health, medical and environmental*

² Lefrançois T., Lina B., Autran B. and members of COVARS *One Health approach at the heart of the French Committee for monitoring and anticipating health risks*, (2023), *Nature Communication* Vol 14 issue 1. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-43089-2>

Autran B., Lefrançois T., & Lina B. (2024). *The COVARS mission: how to anticipate health risks in a "One Health" vision of the exposome*. In: *médecine/sciences* (Vol. 40, Issues 6-7, pp. 485-486). EDP Sciences. <https://doi.org/10.1051/medsci/2024098>

agencies and authorities". In addition, the mission statement of August 17, 2022 specifies that COVARS will work closely with i) "The agencies and authorities responsible for health, medicine and the environment (in particular SPF, HCSP, HAS, ANSES), as well as existing expert committees. Regular meetings of the committee will be scheduled with representatives of health agencies and authorities" and ii) "research and innovation structures, in particular ANRS-MIE and Aviesan, but also the Alliances ALLEnvi and Athéna". Last but not least, "links with international organizations active in regional networks will be established with the Instituts Pasteur network, ANRS-MIE sites, CIRAD networks (dP Caribvet, One Health OI, Grease, RP-PCP) and IRD networks (GDRI, LMI)".

In order to develop this approach, and to work in a climate of trust and serenity necessary for sound and effective anticipation of health risks, it has been essential for COVARS to establish strong and regular meetings with ministers and health and research institutions. Thus, the President, alone or accompanied by the Board, met regularly with:

- **At ministerial level :**
 - *The Ministers of Health and Prevention, Research and Higher Education*, during regular exchanges to explain COVARS' advices and discuss the implementation of recommendations, but also to consider other subjects for referral or self-referral to COVARS,
 - *Directors of ministerial cabinets and ministerial advisors* are also invited to COVARS internal seminars, to present and discuss the working method, approaches, work topics and templates for COVARS advices,
 - *The Director Generals of Health, Healthcare Organization, European and International Affairs and Research and Innovation*, to present details of COVARS recommendations and discuss COVARS work topics.
- **At Prime Minister level:**
 - *the Prime Minister's "Health" advisors* in individual discussions or at inter-ministerial meetings, in order to present COVARS recommendations in greater detail to ministries other than the supervisory ministries, such as Agriculture, the Environment or the Interior; specifically for advices with a strong One Health and territorial organization component.
 - *the Secrétariat Général pour l'Investissement (SGPI)*, as well as with *the Agence d'Innovation en Santé (AIS)*, notably on France 2030's Emerging Diseases and AIS initiatives, in order to present COVARS' advices and discuss possible interactions.
- **At the level of the Presidency of the Republic:**
 - the President's "*Health, Disability*" and "*Research*" advisors to present and discuss COVARS' approaches, work topics and Opinions and their implementation,
- **At the institutional level:**
 - *Health:*
 - *Santé Publique France (SpF) and ANSES*
 - *Haute Autorité de Santé (HAS) and Commission Technique des Vaccinations (CTV)*
 - *Haut Conseil de Santé Publique (HCSP),*
 - *Agence Nationale de Sécurité du Médicament (ANSM),*
 - *Etablissement Français du Sang (EFS).*
 - *Research:* to optimize the scientific watch mission and present and coordinate COVARS' research recommendations with :
 - *ANRS-MIE:* weekly briefings with the agency's CEO on the agency's scientific watch and on COVARS' research recommendations on emerging infectious diseases.

- ANR: through regular meetings with the CEO, notably as part of the ANR Scientific Steering Committee, of which the Chairman is a member,
- Inserm: twice-yearly meetings with the CEO, and more recently with *the Agence de Programme en Santé*,
- Inrae, IRD, CIRAD, CNRS for annual meetings to present COVARS work

c- COVARS internal operating procedures :

i. Main operating principles

The decree of July 30th, 2022 and the COVARS mission statement of August 17th, 2022 establish the central operating principles of the committee:

- **A scientific approach based on facts and scientific evidence:** "COVARS contributes to the production of the expertise required to manage health risks, as mentioned in the last paragraph of article R. 1411-55".

- **A collaborative approach:** described above

- **Confidentiality:** "its members are subject to the confidentiality of debates".

- **Independence:** COVARS members are free of any conflict of interest, and who sit *intuitu personae* for their recognized expertise. In addition, "The Committee carries out its work in complete independence and without any influence from political power", which translates into the Committee's ability to: i) take on any subject it deems important in terms of public health, independently of the agenda and priorities of the supervisory Ministries, and ii) make recommendations it deems useful for monitoring and anticipating health risks, and for the management and preparation of health risks by the French government and institutions.

- **Transparency/publicity of its opinions:** Opinions are made public both on the Ministry of Health and Prevention website³ and on the Ministry of Higher Education and Research website⁴, thereby raising public awareness of health issues.

- **Agility:** COVARS can be mobilized quickly to provide advice on anticipating and managing crises.

ii. Internal organization

COVARS has drawn up an **Operating Charter** (see Appendix 4) and internal operating procedures designed to facilitate work and discussions between members:

- **Establishment of Bureau** (includes the Chairman and two scientific experts: Prof. Bruno Lina and Dr. Thierry Lefrançois) responsible for proposing guidelines and self-referrals, defining the COVARS agenda, finalizing advices and meeting the authorities.
- **Regularity:** The COVARS plenary committee meets weekly on Mondays from 12:30 to 2:30 pm, and in urgent cases, additional meetings may be scheduled. In total, **100 plenary meetings and 100 Bureau meetings** have been organized.
- **Internal brainstorming seminars:** quarterly seminars in Paris enable members to meet face-to-face, identify medium- and long-term health priorities, and fulfill the Group's foresight missions by inviting outside speakers on subjects of general interest (climate, biodiversity). 4 seminars were organized :
 - **January 9th, 2023: Identification of priority risks for the first year of the mandate.** Update on COVARS operations and communications.

³ <https://sante.gouv.fr/actualites/presse/dossiers-de-presse/article/comite-de-veille-et-d-anticipation-des-risques-sanitaires>

⁴ <https://www.enseignementsup-recherche.gouv.fr/fr/accueil-collection/avis-du-covars>

- **April 17th, 2023: Climate change and health**, with Prof. Valérie Masson-Delmotte, Climatologist, member of the HCC and the IPCC, as well as Mélanie le Barbier, Mathilde Pascal, Agnès Verrier from Santé Publique France, and Cyril Caminade, modeller, in the presence of Prof. A. Magnan, Medical Advisor to M. F. Braun.
- **September 25th, 2023: Biodiversity and health**, with Prof. Robert Watson, former Chairman of IPBES and principal author of the UN report "Making peace with nature".
- **April 27th, 2024: Feedback from COVARS' 1st mandate** in the presence of Ms Corine Borel, Deputy DGRI, as well as Mr Cédric Arcos, Cabinet Director and E Malczyk, Health Crisis Advisor, to the Minister of Health.

iii. Procedure for preparing and drafting COVARS advices and notes

To prepare an advice, the initial discussion to define the subject is held at a plenary meeting with all COVARS members. The necessary hearings and expert appraisals are also defined at this/these meeting(s). Following internal discussions, the recommendations are based on available scientific knowledge, with each scientist contributing in his or her respective field of expertise. The drafting and publication of COVARS opinions and notes follow a defined internal procedure (see diagram in appendix 12).

Depending on the subject, a sub-working group is set up, made up of 2 to 3 COVARS members with different areas of expertise, and tasked with coordinating the drafting of the advice, identifying the agencies, research institutes or researchers to be interviewed and conducting the hearings. Together with the working group, the Bureau organizes hearings with various experts from French institutions and structures. To produce its advices and Notes during its first two years of existence, **COVARS held a total of over 130 hearings** (40 for the notes and opinions on Covid-19, including 20 on long covid, 50 for dengue and vector-borne diseases, 30 for HPAI...). Drafting is carried out by the working group and the Project Manager, with the help of the Office.

d- COVARS advices

During this first mandate, **COVARS produced 21 public documents**, an average of 1 document per month:

- **Ten advices**, in response to 4 joint referrals from the Minister of Health and Prevention and the Minister of research, 2 referrals from the Minister of Health and Prevention, and 2 self-referrals. These opinions are the result of an in-depth analysis of a given health issue and include a documented scientific review, an analysis of strengths and weaknesses, and recommendations for decision-makers.
- **Two scoping documents** in response to 2 referrals from the Minister of Health and Prevention, aimed at clarifying the subject of a future opinion and highlighting scientific knowledge to date, prior to drafting the final opinion.
- **Eight notes updating previous advices**. These notes update a previous production on a given subject with new scientific knowledge or recommendations based on developments in the epidemiological situation, or provide a brief review of the current situation and recommendations.
- **A "comment"**: In response to a referral from a supervisory ministry asking COVARS to comment on a document currently being produced.⁵

⁵ Comment on the sheet produced by the MSP, "Analyse et estimation de la population cible des vaccins identifiés par Moderna", in May 2023,

Table 2: COVARS advices and notes published during the first mandate⁶

Main theme	Notice name /note	Submission date	Referral/Self-referral
Covid-19 and Acute Respiratory Infections	Advice on Covid-19	20.10.2022	Joint referral: from Ministers S. Retailleau et F. Braun of 29/09/2022
	Update on the Covid-19 epidemic in the context of influenza and bronchiolitis epidemics - Intermediate note on wearing masks	02.12.2022	
	Covid-19 update	16.12.2022	
	Covid-19 update on the Chinese epidemic	29.12.2022	
	Update on the Covid-19 situation in France	05.04.2023	Minister of Health and Prevention referral on ARI's from the 08.09.2023
	Notice on the fall vaccination campaign against Covid-19 - Part 1/2	15.09.2023	
	Commentary on the national strategy for the prevention and management of viral acute respiratory infections - Part 2/2	04.10.2023	Addition to the joint MESR/MSP referral of 29/09/2022
	Advice on Post-Covid syndrome, its medical, social and economic implications and prospects for improving its management	07.11.2023	
Note on the intensification of the Covid-19 and acute respiratory infection prevention campaign	14.12.2023		
Dengue and vector-borne diseases	Background document on vector-borne diseases (VBDs) in France	23.12.2022	Joint referral by Ministers S. Retailleau and F. Brau from 29.09.2022
	Advice on the health risks of dengue and other Aedes arboviroses in relation to climate change	03.04.2023	
	Background note on the health risks associated with the West-Nile and Usutu viruses	20.10.2023	
	Supplementary advice on the surveillance of West Nile and Usutu viruses in France and the management of infections by these viruses	18.06.2024	
Monkeypox	Advice on the Monkeypox virus epidemic	22.11.2022	Joint referral by Ministers S. Retailleau and F. Braun of 29.09.2022
Highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI)	Advice on the risk of avian influenza linked to Highly Pathogenic Avian Influenza (HPAI)	08.06.2023	Self-referral
	Update on the situation linked to the H5N1 influenza virus (lineage 2.3.4.4b) circulating in the	24.05.2024	

⁶ Unpublished memo: Memo of January 16, 2023 Amended on January 29, 2024 on the health risks engendered by the bill to "control immigration, improve integration

	USA and update of the avian influenza advice of June 8, 2023		
Anticipation	Advice on the future of messenger RNA vaccines in anticipating and managing health crises	09.02.2023	Joint submission by Ministers S. Retailleau and F. Braun from 29.09.2022
	Assessment of the risks of major exceptional health situations for human health in France in the years 2025-2030	03.04.2024	Joint submission by Ministers S. Retailleau and A. Rousseau of 07.12.2023
	Note: Strengthening prevention research and improving citizens' ability to cope with health crises	02.05.2024	Self-referral
	Advice on the development, governance and access to human health databases in anticipation of health crises	26/06/2024	Self-referral
Cholera in Mayotte	Note: Reinforcing the prevention and spread of the Cholera epidemic in Mayotte	07.05.2024	Self-referral

e- Summary of COVARS recommendations

COVARS' recommendations and opinions relate to:

- **Preparing the response to a pandemic** integrating **Prevention, Diagnosis, Treatment, Innovation and Research**, from basic research to more translational research interconnecting human, animal and environmental epidemiology
- **the need for a Surveillance - Research Continuum in a "One Health" approach**, aimed at strengthening, better organizing and interconnecting the analysis of hazards that can affect man and his ecosystems. These two aspects are mutually reinforcing in the event of an outbreak, where research is indispensable to surveillance, as well as in inter-crisis situations, where surveillance benefits from methodological advances and research results (as in the case of the emergen 2.0 project), and research in turn benefits from high-quality surveillance data.
- **the need to support society's informed decision-making through research in the human and social sciences**, to improve understanding of science-society relations, on the one hand by assessing the acceptability of medical or technological innovations on the basis of validated and transparent information and involving communities at territorial and national levels, and on the other, through **education** in health risks and the scientific approach.
- **The international dimension of surveillance and anticipation**, integrating warning signals from abroad and the European and international dimension to health risk prevention and preparedness, enabling the finalization of international agreements and joint pandemic preparedness programs.

COVARS' recommendations focused on points specific to each referral, and included warning points and recurring recommendations summarized in the Tables in Appendix 8 (Table 8-1 for health-related recommendations and Table 8-2 for research-related recommendations). COVARS also stresses the need to

closely link surveillance and research in human, animal and environmental health, at territorial, national and international levels,

The innovative message from COVARS is the need to integrate infectious and environmental risks at all levels of surveillance and preparedness, given their influence on the risk of occurrence, the severity of infectious risks and the vulnerability of populations. **Innovation and research** must be omnipresent in these monitoring, anticipation and preparedness phases, in order to provide public decision-makers with robust foundations on which to base future public surveillance, warning and preparedness policies. Finally, COVARS stresses the need to better coordinate the actions of public decision-makers throughout France, both in mainland France and overseas.

COVARS Health recommendations revolve around 6 major themes:

- Prevention through information, barrier measures and vaccination,
- Monitoring and Detection
- Identifying and protecting the most vulnerable populations
- Research and innovation
- Treat as soon as possible
- Involving and informing society
- Coordinating public action in France and the French overseas territories

COVARS recommendations on surveillance are mainly:

- Decentralizing and strengthening monitoring, diagnosis and management at the animal/human interface
- Strengthening national and international One Health and Exposome monitoring
- Promote real coordination between national, regional and international players
- Anticipate the information system to be deployed in health crisis situations at the care-surveillance-research interface
- Making MOT regulations more flexible
- Involving citizens in the decision-making process concerning health data

COVARS main research recommendations are:

- Improving the responsiveness of French research in times of crisis and between crises
- Interconnecting, structuring and strengthening access to healthcare data
- Promoting interdisciplinary research between the humanities, social sciences and health sciences
- Strengthening integrated "One Health" research
- Taking climate and environmental change into account
- Strengthening research in overseas France
- Reinforce citizen involvement in health risks through research.

f- Communication and publications

i. Institutional distribution of advices

Advices transmission:

Advices and notes are intended primarily for the Ministers to whom COVARS reports, and then for wider distribution directed at institutions, decision-makers, the general public and the media. Advices are generally presented orally at a ministerial meeting, after a preliminary version has been sent for information to

ministerial Cabinets and Advisors, General Directorates Health, Healthcare Organization, Research and Innovation, and the health monitoring agencies involved, a few days before presentation to the Ministers.

Advices are then published on the Ministries' websites.

Each COVARS opinion is then sent to a mailing list adapted to each subject, involving the governing bodies of health agencies and research organizations, as well as key personalities in the fields of health and research, so that these opinions have the necessary impact and scope, reaching and raising the awareness of as many professionals in the country's health sector as possible.

Institutional invitations (appendix 9) :

COVARS was regularly invited to present its advices to Advisors to the President of the Republic and the Prime Minister and to the Ministers of Agriculture, Ecological Transition and the Interior. A summary of COVARS' presentations to health and research institutions can be seen in the table in Appendix 9. In addition, COVARS was invited to present its activities to the French National Assembly (Social Affairs Committee) and the Senate (notably on the occasion of the publication of the opinion on exceptional health risks, and at the 26th national study day on "elected representatives, public health and territories").

ii. Scientific communication (appendix 9)

COVARS has been invited by the scientific community to explain its role, its vision and the content of its advices. Its members have presented COVARS' missions and work at various conferences, round tables and seminars at national and international scientific symposia, the non-exhaustive list of which is given in Appendix 9. COVARS members have also been invited to take part in regional scientific symposia. Finally, COVARS has been the subject of a number of university courses, notably at the Ecole Nationale des Services Vétérinaires.

Publications: COVARS as a committee has been invited to publish in two scientific journals on:

- Le rôle original joué en France par le COVARS pour renforcer la thématique One Health : *One Health approach at the heart of the French Committee for monitoring and anticipating health risks*, Lefrançois T., Lina B., Autran B. et les membres du COVARS (2023), Nature Communication Vol 14 issue 1. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-43089-2> (To read in [appendix 6](#))
- COVARS' vision of anticipating health risks: Autran, B., Lefrancois, T., & Lina, B. (2024). *The COVARS mission: how to anticipate health risks in a "One Health" vision of the exposome*. In médecine/sciences (Vol. 40, Issues 6-7, pp. 485-486). EDP Sciences. <https://doi.org/10.1051/medsci/2024098> (To be read in [appendix 5](#))

iii. Media appearances and communication with the general public (appendix 10)

As part of the transparency of its advices, the committee has sought to explain and comment on its advices to professional audiences and the general public through conferences and press releases, with the help of COVARS' Communications Officer. These were relayed by:

- Professional media (*Quotidien des médecins, Quotidien des pharmaciens, Moniteur des pharmaciens, Medscape, Egora, la Dépêche vétérinaire, la Semaine vétérinaire, le Généraliste, etc.*),
- the general public via the national, regional and even international press: press releases and press conferences have been issued and relayed in TV news, print and online media, and radio broadcasts. COVARS members receive and answer journalists' queries directly, on Avis or on topical issues concerning COVARS' missions.

The 2 non-exhaustive tables in Appendix 10 show COVARS' main appearances in the professional press

(health/veterinary) for the first, and in the national media for the second. Note that these tables exclude appearances in regional media. By way of example, COVARS was mentioned in **154** articles between January 1, 2024 and June 30, 2024, by the main French general-interest media, i.e. around 500-600 media appearances over the two-year term of office.

g- COVARS International Relations

During the 1st year of its mandate, COVARS organized quarterly meetings of the former Covid-19 Scientific Councils of neighboring European countries (Germany, Belgium, Denmark, Spain, Netherlands, , United Kingdom, Switzerland), to monitor epidemiological developments in Covid-19 and Acute Respiratory Infections, and coordinate strategic recommendations. COVARS also invited leading foreign experts such as Prof. J Farrar, Chief Scientist at WHO, for his Opinion on major sanitary situations, and Prof. R Watson, former Chair of IPBES, for a conference on biodiversity. In addition, COVARS has been invited to present its advices to the French Ministry of Health and Prevention's Department of European and International Affairs (DAEI), to the WHO, to the European Agency HERA, to the IPBES and at some 15 scientific symposia.

h- Assessment of COVARS' contribution

i. *From the decision-maker's point of view:*

At the COVARS internal seminar on May 27th, 2024, COVARS members met with Ms Corine Borel, Deputy DGRI, MESR, and Mr C. Arcos, Cabinet Director and E. Malczyk, Conseiller Crise Sanitaire, MSP. The outcome was that COVARS appears as:

- a **useful support point for the government**, actively participating in decision-making,
- a **vehicle for encouraging inter-ministerial work**, thanks to the **multi-disciplinary** skills of COVARS experts, providing a broad spectrum of recommendations, notably for the Ministries of Agriculture, Ecological Transition and the Interior, as well as guidelines and recommendations to help public authorities incorporate the recommendations into action plans.
- **A scientific watch, alerting** the government of potential risks

COVARS offered a contextualized health expertise, thanks to the **spectrum of analysis** provided by COVARS' work in anticipating and responding to crises. It helped to take risks into account on an **international scale**, thanks to its **integrated, global vision** of health risks.

ii. *COVARS as a relay for a One Health approach*

As indicated in the COVARS mission statement (*Appendix 3*), its work should adopt a "One Health" approach⁷. Similarly, the press release issued by the French Ministry of Health when COVARS was set up mentions the

⁷ As defined by OHHLEP (Adisasmito, W. B. One Health High-Level Expert Panel (OHHLEP) et al. One Health: a new definition for a sustainable and healthy future. PLoS Pathog. 18, e1010537 (2022)) and the WHO/WOAH/FAO/UNEP quadripartite (Tripartite and UNEP Support OHHLEP's definition of "One Health". Joint Tripartite (FAO, OIE, WHO) and UNEP Statement. Available at <https://www.who.int/news/item/01-12-2021-tripartite-and-unep-support-ohhlep-s-definition-of-one-health> (2021).)

need for a One Health vision⁸ in order to anticipate tomorrow's health crises, given the interrelationships between emerging diseases and climate change⁹ or biodiversity loss.¹⁰

This One Health approach has guided the composition of COVARS (see part 1.b), which is more multidisciplinary and multi-sectoral than the Covid-19 Scientific Advisory Board and COSV, enabling health risks to be addressed from a variety of angles. Several COVARS members have extensive experience of One Health approaches to environmental, vector-borne and emerging diseases. According to the Ministry of Health's press release of September 29, 2022, "*this composition reflects the diversity of scientific disciplines and approaches needed to monitor and anticipate health risks*".¹¹

The One Health concept is also reflected in the institutional relations of COVARS, which acts as integrator and inter-ministerial vehicle, with frequent contacts with bodies from various sectors:

- national and regional agencies for human, animal and environmental health : ANSES, SPF, HAS, HCSP, DGS, ARS, EFS, ABM, OFB...
- research organizations: Inserm/ANRS-MIE, CIRAD, INRAE, IRD, IP, CNRS, expert groups, etc.
- patient and citizen associations
- The private sector: vaccine and diagnostic test developers, breeding farms, pharmaceutical companies, vector control operators...
- international organizations: WHO, CDC, IPCC, EMA, GISAID, ECDC, etc.

This integrated and One Health vision is present in each advice and note, and is sometimes at the heart of it, as in **the advice on the risks of major Exceptional Health Situations** of April 3, 2024¹², where infectious risks and risks arising from the environment (climate change, chemical substances, loss of biodiversity...) are dealt with in an interdependent manner, the emphasis being placed on the dynamics and interactions between these risks, particularly the increase in :

- vector-borne diseases due to climate change, which has led to a geographical extension of vector zones (including the tiger mosquito and certain ticks)
- respiratory diseases, cancers and other chronic ailments due to pollution,
- zoonoses linked to biodiversity loss.

COVARS' One Health vision was also developed in its opinions on **vector-borne** diseases¹³, which strongly emphasize the need for animal/human/environmental cross-monitoring, as well as in its opinion on **highly pathogenic avian influenza**¹⁴, in which COVARS advocates collaboration between veterinary and human medicine on farms around infected poultry, and the creation of a multidisciplinary structure that can be activated in times of crisis.

⁸ Installation of the Comité de veille et d'anticipation des risques sanitaires (COVARS) 09/29/2022. Available at <https://sante.gouv.fr/actualites/presse/communiqués-de-presse/article/installation-du-comite-de-veille-et-d-anticipation-des-risques-sanitaires>.

⁹ Carlson, C. J. et al. Climate change increases cross-species viral transmission risk. Nature <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-022-04788-w> (2022).

¹⁰ Daszak, P. et al. Workshop Report on Biodiversity and Pandemics of the Intergovernmental Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) (IPBES Secretariat, Bonn, Germany, 2020)

¹¹ <https://sante.gouv.fr/actualites/presse/communiqués-de-presse/article/installation-du-comite-de-veille-et-d-anticipation-des-risques-sanitaires>

¹² Evaluation of the risks of major exceptional health situations for human health in France during the years 2025-2030; response to the MSP's referral of 07.12.2023 relating to the Risques de SSE des 2-5 ans dans une vision One Health

¹³ Opinion on the health risks of dengue and other *Aedes* arboviroses in relation to climate change of April 3, 2023 and Note on the health risks associated with West-Nile and Usutu viruses of October 20, 2023

¹⁴ Opinion on the risk of avian influenza linked to Highly Pathogenic Avian Influenza (HPAI) of June 8, 2023

COVARS has thus played an active role in improving understanding and implementation of the One Health concept in decision-making processes. Communication of COVARS' opinions and notes in the media has helped to spread the concept in society, an assertion supported in an article in *Nature Communication*¹⁵ as well as in the evaluation of French "One Health" actions in the **G7-Santé** declaration of **2023**.

In addition, COVARS has identified public policy weaknesses related to the One Health concept: lack of long-term funding and administrative problems in setting up One Health research, lack of links between human, animal and environmental health databases, silo work, weakness of social science and primary care research on emerging diseases, difficulties in evaluating multidisciplinary research on emerging diseases, or insufficient links between research and human, animal and environmental surveillance.

III. How decision-makers take COVARS recommendations into account

During COVARS' first term of office, follow-up on the implementation of the Committee's recommendations by the decision-maker was carried out in a non-systematic, non-formalized way. This made it more difficult for COVARS to measure the real, on-the-ground impact of its work. This lack of visibility as to whether or not the decision-maker has taken the Committee's recommendations into account could have a negative long-term effect on the involvement of COVARS' members, all of whom are volunteers. The committee has therefore issued recommendations for the development of an interministerial follow-up to its advices and notes for its second term of office, to be found in **section 3**.

However, even in the absence of a formalized follow-up system, several concrete examples demonstrate the contribution of COVARS recommendations in decision-making processes. **Several of COVARS' recommendations have in fact been followed by concrete effects in terms of public policy**, although it is difficult to isolate the effect of COVARS' work from other concordant effects within decision-making processes.

- **Covid-long advice:** COVARS has also helped to shed light on this important subject, which had previously been the subject of little debate. Following the advice, integrated reference centers have been created. Alongside other factors, COVARS has contributed to the organization of the ANRS-MIE Covid-long day, and to the strengthening of HAS discussions on the patient pathway.

- **Advice on Dengue/WN/Usutu viruses:** The DGS has asked the ANSES to define requirements and draw up recommendations for the specifications of a new mosquito reporting site, with a view to upgrading this tool. ANSES has launched a call for applications from scientific experts to form a working group (WG) on "Surveillance of mosquito vectors". (*Reminder of COVARS recommendation: "Redefine the structure and objectives of the ANSES / DGS "signalement moustique "11 website, the first mosquito reporting tool open to the whole population."*)

- **Advice on Highly Pathogenic Avian Influenza:** Several of the recommendations in the 2023 opinion have been followed by concrete action, such as *"Raising awareness and convincing all players of the importance of vaccinating farm animals against the zoonotic risk of AI"; "Supporting the preventive vaccination strategy recommended by the anses"; "Evaluating the animal and human vaccination policy"; "Extending the HAS seasonal vaccination recommendation to OFB staff and hunters in contact with at-risk animals and their entourage"....*

¹⁵ Lefrançois T., Lina B., Autran B. and members of COVARS (2023), One Health approach at the heart of the French Committee for monitoring and anticipating health risks, *Nature Communication* Vol 14 issue 1. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-43089-2>

In the field of research, there are several examples of the positive influence of COVARS advices. This is notably the case for the recommendation to assess vaccine efficacy in the **advice on Covid-19** of October 2022, followed by the implementation by ANRS, SPF and EpiPhare of a study on the assessment of vaccine efficacy and 2 publications by SPF¹⁶. Similarly, **the advice on Exceptional Health Situations (EHS)** of April 2024 led to an alignment with COVARS recommendations on the next call for research proposals from the University of Montpellier's ExposUM Institute entitled "Anticipation of exposomic health risks".

Overall, **each of COVARS' advices and notes offers intangible, non-measurable benefits as they help to shed light on the subject in question.** For example, several COVARS self-investigations have indirectly led to the organization of meetings, symposia or seminars (and the choice of guests), as well as reinforcing the weight and legitimacy of certain scientific arguments. For example, in the context of arboviruses, COVARS has contributed to a real awareness of the environmental and veterinary dimension, which is now more present than ever in scientific discussions.

¹⁶ Including Auvigne, V. et al (2023). *Protection against symptomatic SARS-CoV-2 infection conferred by the Pfizer-BioNTech Original/BA.4-5 bivalent vaccine compared to the mRNA Original monovalent vaccines - A matched cohort study in France.* In Vaccine (Vol. 41, Issue 38, pp. 5490-5493)

III. Recommendations for COVARS' second term of office

a. Health risk analysis proposals for the next mandate

At the end of its quarterly seminar on May 27, 2024, COVARS recommended amplifying future work on **health risks related to climate change and the exposome**, on the one hand, and **mental health**, on the other, subjects that were insufficiently developed during the 1st mandate, as COVARS advices focused mainly on infectious risks.

Table 6: Health risks and anticipation identified by COVARS for a future mandate

	<i>Topics of interest</i>	<i>Sub-themes</i>
HEALTH RISKS AND SOCIETY	MENTAL HEALTH AND EMERGING RISKS	- Climate crisis and eco-anxiety - Mental health for all, especially children and young adults
	EDUCATION AND HEALTH	- Education on health and health risks, especially directed at young people - Fake news and misinformation
ENVIRONMENT AND HEALTH	GLOBAL CHANGES (Climate, biodiversity)	- Infectious diseases - Water-related diseases and eco-toxicities - Emergences - Food-related health risks
	EXPOSOME	- Risks of chronic inflammatory diseases, cancer - Health consequences of exposure to pollutants at individual and population levels.
	DEMOGRAPHIC CHANGES	- Health risks linked to ageing, urbanization and population movements
HEALTH RISKS AND THE HEALTHCARE SYSTEM	ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE	
	DRUG SHORTAGES AND STOCKOUTS	
	CARE SYSTEMS	- Response from the healthcare system. Particularly the question of caregivers, but also the ecosystem approach
INFECTIOUS RISKS	EMERGENCES	- Typology, impact, mechanisms; sharing pathogen genomic data
	FOLLOW-UP AND UPDATING OF PREVIOUS NOTICES	-Exceptional health situations - Pandemic influenza - Health databases - Prevention (including vaccines) - Monitoring systems
ANTICIPATE	PREVENTION RESEARCH	- Vaccines - SHS: Information, involvement of society

THANKS TO RESEARCH	SIMPLIFICATION	- Regulatory processes, mock-up protocols...
	AMBULATORY RESEARCH	- Development of ambulatory research platforms
	PARTICIPATORY SCIENCE	

b. Future composition: Disciplinary expertise to be internalized for COVARS' second mandate

Despite the current diversity of COVARS' scientific and medical expertise, **the committee needs to be enriched with additional expertise in the non-infectious, environmental and societal fields**, so as to broaden the range of subjects to be addressed, while maintaining existing expertise on the infectious component of health risks. The following areas of expertise seem essential to be strengthened for the second mandate:

- **Ecotoxicology,**
- **Mental health**
- **Digital domain**

For a second mandate, it therefore seems essential **to increase the number of scientific experts to around twenty** (instead of the current 16) in order to respond more effectively to the above-mentioned issues. External expertise will also be required on an ad hoc basis, particularly in health economics and health/precarity, as stipulated in the mission statement (see Appendix 3), which states that COVARS may "*call on ad hoc medical-scientific expertise depending on the nature of the risks involved*". *"In this context, COVARS will set up complementary thematic groups drawn from disciplines not permanently represented within its membership"*.

c. Areas for improvement in the COVARS organization :

All COVARS members, all volunteers and satisfied with the internal operation despite the heavy workload which limits the capacity for mobilization in the medium/long term, suggested the following points for improvement:

- **Frequency of plenary meetings:** less frequent meetings and more individualized working groups would be more compatible with members' professional lives, but with the risk of splitting up by discipline and breaking the unity of the committee.
- **Resolve problems of publication deadlines** on Ministry websites, particularly Health (in connection with changes in the Ministry and the person responsible for cabinet communications at the MSP).
- **Disseminate notices more widely in the healthcare sector**, particularly the regional administrations (including ARS). The current distribution list only includes the heads of the main institutions/agencies. Communication should be extended both horizontally (number of institutions targeted to be increased) and vertically (transmission to all levels).
- **Develop communication aimed at the general public/civil society:** current communication is essentially based on press conferences, which are inaccessible to the general public. It would be useful to develop the practice of providing summaries of COVARS advices on the Ministry of Health website, along the lines of what is done by the DIRCOM of the MESR (French Ministry of Higher Education and Research).

d. Areas for improvement in institutional relations

i. Relations with supervisory ministries :

It is necessary to strengthen and systematize dialogue and discussion between COVARS and each of its supervisory ministries, with a dual aim: to increase decision-makers' awareness of the issues addressed and its recommendations, and, conversely, to enable COVARS to better grasp the issues at stake in public decision-making and the feasibility of its recommendations. This strengthening of relations between COVARS and its supervisory ministries could be achieved in particular by :

- **Organizing a system for monitoring and evaluating COVARS recommendations**, with systematic biannual analysis organized on an inter-ministerial basis.
- **Sharing a work schedule with the supervisory ministries on the topics to be dealt with**, in order to discuss a possible transformation from self-referral to referral, clarifying COVARS' position vis-à-vis other agencies, in particular health agencies, and avoiding redundant referrals with those of other institutions.
- **Reinforcing joint exchanges between COVARS and its two supervisory ministries**, to better identify common/transversal needs. With the Research Ministry, as proposed by C. Borel, Deputy DGRI, **quarterly meetings could be planned**, involving other research stakeholders, such as the Agence de programme en Santé, the scientific programming community/the PEPRs of major programs (notably prevention).

ii. With national and international health and research institutions

- **Links with public health stakeholders:** A clarification of competencies with other public health bodies would be necessary
- **Links with research stakeholders:** More direct interaction with research agencies and researchers would be desirable. COVARS members would also like to see links with the Presidential Science Council.
- **International links:** A stronger international link is desirable, with regular contacts with international health monitoring agencies and bodies similar to COVARS in other European countries (such as SAGE in the UK, or the new crisis committee in Spain).
- **Links with society:** The link between COVARS and society is essentially established via two channels: **i)** COVARS members representing patient associations and citizens **ii)** the major media when advices are published. In the future, COVARS would benefit from strengthening its links with citizens, through the organization of meetings with major associations, or COVARS' participation in possible citizen conventions.

IV Conclusion:

COVARS' strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats for future improvement are summarized below:

STRENGTHS

Internal factors

- ◆ **Direct link to decision-makers** (Ministers, Cabinets) enabling a real **science-decision interface**
- ◆ **Close links with health and research institutions**, enabling us to act as an **integrator of recommendations and data** from the various agencies
- ◆ **Multidisciplinarity and strong representation of health democracy**, enabling a One Health vision
- ◆ **Independence and self-referral**, enabling the committee to act as an **early warning system** for the government
- ◆ **Agility** for rapid response and advice
- ◆ Strong group **cohesion** and work dynamics linked to its small size
- ◆ **Territorial** anchoring thanks to members' networks and consideration of **specific territorial features** (particularly overseas)

WEAKNESSES

- ◆ **Weak follow-up on implementation of COVARS recommendations** and absence of a real implementation mechanism
- ◆ **The interministerial link is not systematized enough**, given COVARS' missions and transversal recommendations
- ◆ **Insufficient number and diversity of experts** for COVARS' missions (particularly environmental)
- ◆ **Insufficiently systematic feedback** of health monitoring information
- ◆ **Insufficient human resources** to carry out the scientific watch mission
- ◆ **Dissemination of reviews and ratings** still too low in professional networks and among the general public
- ◆ Underdeveloped **international links and links with research players**

OPPORTUNITIES

External factors

- ◆ **Reinforcement of :**
 - **relations with Ministers**, their offices, PM and PR advisors, hitherto fluid and regular, and practices in keeping with "good politics".
 - **links with research**, thanks to the new program agencies and the ANR,
 - **international collaborations**: in particular, the creation of committees similar to COVARS in Europe and collaboration with the DAEI on the global health strategy for the G7-Santé.
- ◆ **COVARS opinion on major exceptional health situations**, offering the opportunity to :
 - structuring the State's implementation of recommendations
 - COVARS begins work on environmental risks

THREATS

- ◆ **Integration of COVARS in its institutional environment: Complexity** in the event of political instability and ministerial reshuffles
- ◆ **Dissociation of time and expectations** between science, politics and societal demands
- ◆ **Delays** (or even absence) **publishing** notices on ministry websites, and risks of reducing the impact of notices.
- ◆ **COVARS' position** in relation to other health authorities not very formalised
- ◆ **Health watch data feedback**: deterioration due to weak links between COVARS and institutions
- ◆ **Long-term mobilization of members** weakened by the volunteer principle

In conclusion, during its first term of office, COVARS developed its role as a scientific advisory body on the monitoring and anticipation of health risks, working closely with the French Ministries of Health and Research, thanks to its structure, independence, multidisciplinary composition, direct access to decision-makers and resources.

COVARS has played an integrating role at the Science-Decision-Society interface, following a transdisciplinary approach, from medicine to ecology. This was made possible by the diversity of its membership and the proactive implementation of the One Health approach, allowing a broad, multi-sectoral opening of COVARS' recommendations and opinions:

- taking into account all the determinants of human health in conjunction with animal and environmental health,
- Making wide-ranging recommendations requiring an **interministerial approach**. This interministerial approach, necessary in periods of anticipation and inter-crisis preparation, will need to be reinforced in crisis situations, as it was during the Covid-19 pandemic.

Points for improvement are suggested in this document (see part 3), such as :

- **strengthening COVARS' work on environmental and socially-related health risks**, while maintaining its expertise in infectious risks,
- a **minimal expansion of COVARS' membership**, currently limited in number by decree and a key factor in its cohesion and agility,
- **a stronger link with research**, to anticipate health risks, thanks to the new research agencies,
- **a strengthening of COVARS' international interactions**, necessary for anticipating and preparing for health crises, currently limited by the absence of European and international interlocutors of the same nature as COVARS, but which should evolve if other countries follow the COVARS model.

This first COVARS mandate has confirmed the usefulness of this type of advice for public decision-makers, in conjunction with health and research institutions, and has shown the importance of the integrator activity of the committee.

Appendices :

Appendix 1: Decree establishing COVARS

Appendix 2: By-laws appointing the Chair and members of the committee

Appendix 3: COVARS mission statement

Appendix 4: COVARS operating charter

Appendix 5: Editorial in Médecine/Science - "COVARS' mission: how to anticipate health risks in a 'One Health' vision of the exposome".

Appendix 6: Commentary in Nature communication on Covars' One Health approach (available [here](#))

Appendix 7: Tasks assigned to COVARS human resources

Appendix 8: Summary of COVARS' main recommendations

Appendix 9: COVARS institutional and scientific communications

Appendix 10: COVARS media appearances

Appendix 11: Table of COVARS' main recommendations concerning arboviroses and HPAI

Appendix 12: Outline of the procedure for drafting advices and notes

Appendix 1: Decree establishing COVARS

31 juillet 2022

JOURNAL OFFICIEL DE LA RÉPUBLIQUE FRANÇAISE

Texte 49 sur 98

Décrets, arrêtés, circulaires

TEXTES GÉNÉRAUX

MINISTÈRE DE LA SANTÉ ET DE LA PRÉVENTION

Décret n° 2022-1099 du 30 juillet 2022 instituant
un comité de veille et d'anticipation des risques sanitaires

NOR : SPRZ2222696D

Publics concernés : acteurs du système de santé, autorités publiques.*Objet* : création d'un comité de veille et d'anticipation des risques sanitaires.*Entrée en vigueur* : le texte entre en vigueur le lendemain de sa publication.*Notice* : le décret crée un comité de veille et d'anticipation des risques sanitaires, chargé d'anticiper et de suivre l'évolution des menaces sanitaires ainsi que d'émettre des avis sur la stratégie à adopter pour lutter contre ces menaces. Il fixe sa composition, ses missions et ses modalités de fonctionnement.*Références* : le décret ainsi que les dispositions du code de la santé publique qu'il crée peuvent être consultés sur le site Légifrance (<https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr>).

La Première ministre,

Sur le rapport de la ministre de l'enseignement supérieur et de la recherche et du ministre de la santé et de la prévention,

Vu le code des relations entre le public et l'administration, notamment ses articles R. 133-3 à R. 133-15 ;

Vu le code de la santé publique, notamment ses articles L. 1313-1 et R. 1411-55 ;

Vu la loi n° 2022-1089 du 30 juillet 2022 mettant fin aux régimes d'exception créés pour lutter contre l'épidémie liée à la covid 19, notamment son article 3, ensemble la décision n° 2022-840 DC du 30 juillet 2022 du Conseil constitutionnel ;

Vu le décret n° 2006-781 du 3 juillet 2006 fixant les conditions et les modalités de règlement des frais occasionnés par les déplacements temporaires des personnels civils de l'Etat,

Décrète :

Art. 1^{er}. – Le chapitre III du titre I^{er} du livre IV de la première partie (partie réglementaire) du code de la santé publique est complété par une section 11 ainsi rédigée :

« Section 11

« Comité de veille et d'anticipation des risques sanitaires

« Art. D. 1413-92. – Un comité de veille et d'anticipation des risques sanitaires est institué auprès des ministres chargés de la santé et de la recherche. Ce comité est chargé :

« 1° D'assurer une veille scientifique sur les risques sanitaires liés aux agents infectieux atteignant l'homme et l'animal, aux polluants environnementaux et alimentaires, et au changement climatique ;

« 2° De modéliser les données recueillies dans le cadre de sa mission de veille scientifique et d'établir des projections ;

« 3° D'émettre des recommandations lorsqu'une projection fait apparaître un risque sanitaire ;

« 4° D'émettre des recommandations sur les mesures envisagées par les autorités publiques afin de lutter contre une crise sanitaire ;

« 5° D'émettre, en tant que de besoin, des recommandations sur la stratégie vaccinale mise en œuvre, le cas échéant, face à une menace sanitaire identifiée par le comité.

« Il peut, pour l'exercice de ses missions, se prononcer de sa propre initiative ou être saisi par l'un des ministres auprès desquels il est institué.

« Il est l'autorité scientifique compétente mentionnée aux I et II de l'article 3 de la loi du 30 juillet 2022 susvisée. Il est saisi à ce titre par le ministre chargé de la santé.

« Ses membres sont soumis à la confidentialité des débats.

« Ses avis sont rendus publics.

« *Art. D. 1413-93.* – Le comité mentionné à l'article D. 1413-92 est présidé par une personnalité qualifiée désignée par les ministres auprès desquels il est institué.

« Il est composé, en outre, sur proposition de son président :

« 1° De seize personnalités scientifiques ou professionnels de santé ;

« 2° D'un représentant des patients ;

« 3° D'un représentant des citoyens.

« En cas de crise sanitaire, le président du comité peut proposer de faire appel à des personnalités supplémentaires pour leurs expertises spécifiques.

« Le président et les membres du comité sont nommés par arrêté des ministres auprès desquels il est institué pour une durée de deux ans, renouvelable une fois.

« *Art. D. 1413-94.* – Le comité exerce ses missions en toute indépendance.

« Les travaux du comité sont menés en lien avec les structures de recherche et d'innovation existantes, ainsi qu'avec les agences et autorités compétentes en matière sanitaire, médicale, environnementale. Il contribue à la production de l'expertise nécessaire à la gestion des risques sanitaires mentionnée au dernier alinéa de l'article R. 1411-55.

« Pour l'exercice de ses missions, il a accès à l'évaluation des risques mentionnée à l'antépénultième alinéa de L. 1313-1.

« Ses réunions peuvent se tenir sous forme dématérialisée. »

Art. 2. – Sont abrogés :

– le décret du 3 avril 2020 portant nomination du président du comité de scientifiques constitué au titre de l'état d'urgence sanitaire déclaré pour faire face à l'épidémie de covid-19 ;

– le décret du 3 avril 2020 portant nomination des membres du comité de scientifiques constitué au titre de l'état d'urgence sanitaire déclaré pour faire face à l'épidémie de covid-19 ;

– le décret du 16 février 2021 portant nomination de membres du comité de scientifiques constitué au titre de l'état d'urgence sanitaire déclaré pour faire face à l'épidémie de covid-19.

Art. 3. – La ministre de l'enseignement supérieur et de la recherche et le ministre de la santé et de la prévention sont chargés, chacun en ce qui le concerne, de l'exécution du présent décret, qui sera publié au *Journal officiel* de la République française.

Fait le 30 juillet 2022.

ÉLISABETH BORNE

Par la Première ministre :

*Le ministre de la santé
et de la prévention,*

FRANÇOIS BRAUN

*La ministre de l'enseignement supérieur
et de la recherche,*
SYLVIE RETAILLEAU

Appendix 2: By-laws appointing the Chair and members of COVARS

17 août 2022

JOURNAL OFFICIEL DE LA RÉPUBLIQUE FRANÇAISE

Texte 97 sur 120

Décrets, arrêtés, circulaires

MESURES NOMINATIVES

MINISTÈRE DE LA SANTÉ ET DE LA PRÉVENTION

Arrêté du 16 août 2022 portant nomination au comité de veille et d'anticipation des risques sanitaires institué à l'article D. 1413-92 du code de la santé publique

NOR : SPRZ2224041A

Par arrêté de la ministre de l'enseignement supérieur et de la recherche et du ministre de la santé et de la prévention en date du 16 août 2022, Mme Brigitte AUTRAN est nommée présidente du comité de veille et d'anticipation des risques sanitaires.

RÉPUBLIQUE FRANÇAISE

Ministère de la santé et de la prévention

Arrêté du

portant nomination au comité de veille et d'anticipation des risques sanitaires institué à l'article D. 1413-92 du code de la santé publique

NOR : SPRZ2227174A

La ministre de l'enseignement supérieur et de la recherche et le ministre de la santé et de la prévention,

Vu le code de la santé publique, notamment ses articles D. 1413-92 et D. 1413-93,

Arrêtent :

Article 1^{er}

Sont nommés membres du comité de veille et d'anticipation des risques sanitaires :

1° Au titre des personnalités scientifiques ou des professionnels de santé, en application du 1° de l'article D. 1413-93 du code de la santé publique :

M. Fabrice Carrat
 M. Simon Cauchemez
 Mme Julie Contenti
 M. Xavier de Lamballerie
 Mme Annabel Desgrees du Lou
 M. Didier Fontenille
 M. Patrick Giraudoux
 Mme Mélanie Heard
 M. Thierry Lefrançois
 M. Roger Le Grand
 M. Xavier Lescure
 M. Bruno Lina
 M. Denis Malvy
 M. Olivier Saint-Lary
 M. Rémi Slama

2° Au titre des représentants des patients, en application du 2° du même article D. 1413-93 :

Mme Yvanie Caillé

Mme Cécile Offerlé

3° Au titre de représentant des citoyens, en application du 3° dudit article D. 1413-93 :

Mme Véronique Loyer

Article 2

Le présent arrêté sera publié au *Journal officiel* de la République française.

Fait le

Le ministre la santé et de la prévention

François BRAUN

La ministre de l'enseignement supérieur
et de la recherche

Sylvie RETAILLEAU

Appendix 3: COVARS mission statement

Les Ministres

Paris, le Mercredi 17 août 2022

Madame la Professeure,

Avec la fin des dispositions relatives à l'état d'urgence sanitaire, le conseil scientifique COVID (CS) et le comité d'orientation de la stratégie vaccinale (COSV) ont disparu le 31 juillet 2022. Le CS avait été mis en place le 10 mars 2020 et officialisé par un décret le 3 avril 2020 sous le nom de « comité de scientifiques constitué à titre de l'urgence sanitaire » en application de la loi n° 2020-290 du 23 mars 2020 d'urgence pour faire face à l'épidémie de Covid-19. Le COSV était un autre conseil indépendant consultatif créé le 3 décembre 2020 par le Premier Ministre afin d'assister le Gouvernement sur la conception de la campagne vaccinale, placé auprès du ministre des Solidarités et de la Santé.

En relais de ces deux instances, nous avons proposé la création d'un Comité de Veille et d'Anticipation des Risques Sanitaires (COVARS), également consultatif et indépendant, mais pérenne, indépendant de tout état d'urgence.

Nous souhaitons vous confier la mission de présider ce comité.

Placé auprès des ministres chargés de la recherche et de la santé, le COVARS sera une instance d'expertise mise à la disposition du Gouvernement pour l'aider dans ses décisions en lien avec les crises sanitaires. Il sera composé, outre son président, de quinze professionnels de santé et/ou de scientifiques représentatifs des diverses disciplines impliquées dans ses missions, d'un représentant des patients et de deux représentants des citoyens.

Nous souhaitons résolument que le COVARS inscrive son travail dans le contexte « Une seule santé » (« One Health »). A la suite de la pandémie COVID et à l'aune des risques plus larges désormais identifiés (environnementaux, alimentaires, climatiques...), son périmètre concernera en effet non seulement le risque infectieux chez l'homme et l'animal (dont les zoonoses possiblement transmissibles à l'homme), mais aussi les risques liés aux pollutions environnementales de l'air, de la terre et de l'eau, et au changement climatique, parmi lesquelles les infections prédominent.

Professeure Brigitte AUTRAN
Hôpital Pitié-Salpêtrière
Département d'immunologie
47-83 Boulevard de l'Hôpital
75013 Paris

En revanche, sont exclus du champ de veille et d'action du COVARS les risques relevant de la défense nationale et la sécurité intérieure, tels que le risque nucléaire, les risques liés à une fuite, accidentelle ou non, de produits chimiques, ou au bioterrorisme.

Pérenne, le COVARS travaillera en dehors des crises aux enjeux d'anticipation et de prévention des crises sanitaires et leurs conséquences (veille scientifique, prédiction et modélisation, recommandations pour réduire le risque et prendre en charge et accompagner nos concitoyens). Lors des crises, il pourra être élargi pour s'adjoindre les meilleures expertises au vu des enjeux posés, et devenir instance de conseil pour le Gouvernement.

Son fonctionnement sera fondé sur 4 principes forts :

- **Consultatif.** Le COVARS aura vocation à éclairer l'exécutif, seul responsable de la décision et de la mise en œuvre opérationnelle.
- **Indépendant.** Le COVARS sera constitué d'experts libres de tout conflit d'intérêt siégeant *intuitu personae* pour leur expertise reconnue. Leurs prises de position n'engageront en rien les institutions auxquelles ils appartiennent. Le COVARS aura la capacité de s'auto-saisir selon les risques potentiels qu'il identifiera. Les membres du COVARS s'engageront à conserver la plus stricte confidentialité aux débats.
- **Transparent.** Ses avis seront rendus publics.
- **Agile.** Le COVARS sera rapidement mobilisable pour rendre des avis en rapport avec l'anticipation et la gestion des crises.

Le COVARS pourra, pour l'exercice de ses missions, se prononcer de sa propre initiative ou être saisi par l'un des ministres auprès desquels il est institué. Il sera libre de s'entourer des expertises médico-scientifiques *ad hoc* selon la nature des risques caractérisés. Le COVARS constituera dans ce cadre des groupes complémentaires thématiques issus de disciplines non représentées de manière permanente en son sein (ex : groupe santé-environnement, groupe risques psycho-sociaux des crises sanitaires, groupe recherche en période de crise sanitaire etc ...). Vous identifierez les comités d'experts ou les experts à mobiliser en cas de crise sanitaire.

Pour l'accomplissement de votre mission, les Ministères mettront à votre disposition des moyens de secrétariat administratif, de veille bibliographique et rédaction d'avis, et de communication.

Concernant les liens du COVARS avec les autres organismes, les travaux du comité seront menés en lien avec les structures de recherche et d'innovation existantes, ainsi qu'avec les agences et autorités compétentes en matière sanitaire, médicale, environnementale. Il travaillera en lien rapproché avec les agences et hauts comités concernés, et aura accès à l'évaluation des risques qu'ils effectuent.

Ainsi, le COVARS travaillera en étroite liaison avec :

- Les **agences et autorités compétentes en matière sanitaire, médicale, environnementale** (notamment SPF, HCSP, HAS, ANSES) ainsi que les comités d'experts* existants. Des réunions régulières du comité seront programmées avec les représentants des agences et autorités de santé (notamment SPF, HAS, HCSP, ANSES, ANSM, DGS).
- Les structures de recherche et d'innovation, en particulier ANRS-MIE et Aviesan** mais aussi notamment les Alliances de recherche sur l'Environnement (ALLEnvi) et en Sciences humaines et Sociales (Athéna).

Le lien avec les organismes présents à l'international dans le cadre de réseaux régionaux sera effectué avec le Réseau des Instituts Pasteur, les sites ANRS-MIE, les réseaux du CIRAD (dP Caribvet, One Health OI, Grease, RP-PCP...) ou de l'IRD (GDRI, LMI...).

Vous partagerez des informations avec les comités scientifiques ou structures européennes et internationales, ou d'autres pays partageant le même mandat de veille et d'anticipation des risques sanitaires.

Nous aurons des entrevues régulières avec vous et le bureau. Vous aurez aussi, en tant que de besoin, à rencontrer les représentants du ministère chargé de l'agriculture et du ministère chargé de la transition écologique, ainsi que le cabinet de la Première ministre, afin d'assurer une vision interministérielle.

Nous vous remercions vivement de mettre votre expertise scientifique au service de la nation dans cette perspective d'anticipation des crises, et nous vous adressons nos vœux les plus chaleureux de réussite dans l'exercice de votre mission.

François BRAUN

Sylvie RETAILLEAU

* groupes d'expertise de l'anses <https://www.anses.fr/fr/content/avis-et-rapports-d-expertise-santé-environnement>:

Biotechnologie ; Eaux ; Perturbateurs endocriniens. Évaluation des risques chimiques liés aux articles et produits de consommation, aux agents physiques et aux nouvelles technologies (climat inclus ds agents physiques), aux milieux aériens

** Organismes entrant dans la composition d'AVIESAN et susceptibles d'interagir avec le Comité : CEA, RESEAU CHU, CNRS, France UNIVERSITES, INRAE, INRIA, INSERM, INSTITUT PASTEUR, IRD, ARIIS, CDEFI, CIRAD, EFS, FONDATION MERIEUX, INERIS, INSTITUT CURIE, INSTITUT MINES TELECOM, IRBA, IRSI, UNICANCER

Appendix 4: COVARS operating charter

Charte du Comité de Veille et d'Anticipation des Risques Sanitaires (COVARS)

Le Comité de Veille et d'Anticipation des Risques Sanitaires (COVARS) a été créé sous l'égide de M. le Ministre de la Santé et de la Prévention et de Mme la Ministre de l'Enseignement Supérieur et de la Recherche (Décret no 2022-1099 du 30 juillet 2022) en relais du Conseil Scientifique COVID (CS) et du Comité d'Orientation de la Stratégie Vaccinale (COSV) disparus le 31 juillet 2022 avec la fin des dispositions relatives à l'état d'urgence sanitaire lié à la pandémie de Covid-19.

Le COVARS est consultatif et indépendant, mais pérenne.

I- Rôle et Missions

Conjointement placé auprès des ministères chargés de la Santé et de la Recherche, le COVARS est une instance d'expertise mise à la disposition du gouvernement pour l'aider dans ses décisions en lien avec les crises sanitaires.

- Il inscrit son travail dans une approche « Une seule santé » (« One Health ») non seulement sur le risque infectieux chez l'homme, y compris zoonotique, mais aussi sur les risques liés aux pollutions environnementales de l'air, de la terre et de l'eau, et au changement climatique, ou à l'alimentation. Sont exclus du champ de veille et d'action du COVARS les risques relevant de la défense nationale et la sécurité intérieure, tels que le risque nucléaire, les risques liés à une dissémination accidentelle ou intentionnelle de produits chimiques ou au bioterrorisme.
- en dehors des crises le COVARS travaille aux enjeux d'anticipation et de prévention des crises sanitaires et leurs conséquences (veille scientifique, prédiction et modélisation, recommandations pour réduire le risque et prendre en charge et accompagner nos concitoyens, mise en place des moyens de la réponse, anticipation sur les contremesures nécessaires).
- Lors des crises, il pourra être élargi pour s'adjoindre les meilleures expertises au vu des enjeux posés, et devenir force de proposition rapprochée pour le Gouvernement.

II- Fonctionnement

Le fonctionnement du Covars est fondé sur 4 principes:

- **Consultatif.** Le COVARS a vocation à éclairer l'exécutif, seul responsable de la décision et de la mise en œuvre opérationnelle.
- **Indépendant.** Le COVARS est constitué d'experts libres de tout conflit d'intérêt siégeant *intuitu personae* pour leur expertise reconnue. Leurs prises de position n'engagent en rien les institutions auxquelles ils appartiennent. Le COVARS a la capacité de s'auto-saisir selon les risques potentiels qu'il identifie dans ses domaines de compétences.
- **Transparent.** Ses avis sont rendus publics et communiqués dans les plus courts délais par les ministères concernés. Le COVARS pourra restituer le contenu de ses avis lors de Conférence de Presse. Les avis du COVARS mentionnent le nom des experts qui ont effectivement participé à leur réalisation, la liste des personnes auditionnées, et les avis minoritaires sont publiés avec le ou les nom/s des porteurs de ces avis minoritaires.
- **Agile.** Le COVARS est rapidement mobilisable par les ministères ou sur auto-saisine pour rendre des avis en rapport avec l'anticipation et la gestion des crises.

Le COVARS fonctionne sous un format unique plénier. Ses réunions sont hebdomadaires. Pour faciliter son fonctionnement, il met en place un bureau de trois personnalités du COVARS en charge notamment de l'interaction régulière avec les ministères, agences et organismes d'Etat.

Les membres du COVARS sont tenus à la discrétion et à la confidentialité sur les travaux et discussions menés par le groupe. Les personnes auditionnées ponctuellement sont informées de la confidentialité des travaux. Lors de communications individuelles sollicitées par la Presse ou par tout autre moyen rendant leurs avis public, les membres du COVARS conservent leur liberté de parole à titre individuel. Ils doivent en faire clairement état lors de la communication.

Les travaux du COVARS sont menés en lien avec les :

- Organismes nationaux : le COVARS travaille en étroite liaison avec :
 - Les agences et autorités compétentes en matière sanitaire, médicale, environnementale (notamment SPF, HCSP, HAS, ANSES) ainsi que les comités d'experts* existants. Des réunions régulières du comité seront programmées avec les représentants des agences et autorités de santé (notamment SPF, HCSP, HAS, ANSES, ANSM, DGS).
 - Les structures de recherche et d'innovation, en particulier ANRS-MIE et Aviesan** mais aussi notamment les Alliances de recherche sur l'Environnement (ALLEnvi) et en Sciences humaines et Sociales (Athéna).

Le COVARS a accès à l'évaluation des risques que ces organismes effectuent

- Organismes nationaux présents à l'international dans le cadre de réseaux régionaux tels que le Réseau des Instituts Pasteur, les sites ANRS-MIE, les réseaux du CIRAD ou de l'IRD.
- Comités scientifiques ou structures européennes et internationales, ou d'autres pays partageant le même mandat de veille et d'anticipation des risques sanitaires avec lesquels le COVARS partage des informations sous couvert d'accords de confidentialité.

La Présidente et le bureau du COVARS auront des entrevues régulières avec les Ministres dont il relève ainsi qu'avec, en tant que de besoin, les conseillers du Président de la République et de la Première Ministre, et les représentants des autres ministères notamment chargés de l'agriculture et de la transition écologique. afin d'assurer une vision interministérielle. Ces entrevues doivent permettre notamment de préciser le contenu des saisines et leur calendrier.

Des moyens de secrétariat administratif, de veille bibliographique et rédaction d'avis, et de communication sont mis à disposition du COVARS par les Ministères pour l'accomplissement de ces missions. Les mêmes obligations de confidentialité sont assignées aux personnes associées au fonctionnement du COVARS et assistant aux réunions.

Les activités d'expertise du COVARS sont faites à titre bénévole. En cas de déplacement des membres du COVARS ou d'experts extérieurs pour des réunions, les membres et experts sont indemnisés de leurs frais de déplacement et de séjour dans les conditions prévues pour les personnels civils de l'Etat.

III- Composition

Le COVARS est composé, outre sa présidente, de seize professionnels de santé et/ou de scientifiques représentatifs des diverses disciplines impliquées dans ses missions, de deux représentants des patients et d'un représentant des citoyens, ayant un mandat de deux ans. La composition est proposée par son président aux ministères concernés, et leur nomination est entérinée par Décret.

Le COVARS peut s'entourer à tout moment des expertises médico-scientifiques *ad hoc* selon la nature des risques caractérisés.

Les membres proposés font, avant leur intégration, une déclaration publique d'intérêts mentionnant notamment leurs liens directs ou indirects avec les entreprises, établissements ou organismes dont les activités s'inscrivent dans un domaine pouvant faire l'objet des travaux du COVARS. Cette déclaration est établie sur le modèle du formulaire figurant en annexe de l'arrêté du 31 mars 2017 portant fixation du document type de la déclaration publique d'intérêts (DPI) mentionnée à l'article L. 1451-1 du code de la santé publique (CSP). Elle est renseignée et signée sur le site <https://dpi.sante.gouv.fr/>. Les déclarations publiques d'intérêts des membres sont actualisées à l'initiative des déclarants et dans tous les cas actualisées chaque année.

IV- Engagement des Membres du COVARS

Les membres du conseil :

- sont présents à titre personnel,
- s'appuient sur une expertise fondée sur l'analyse des données scientifiques et des études de différentes disciplines, y compris en sciences humaines,
- respectent la confidentialité des échanges au sein du conseil et des informations transmises par les pouvoirs publics,
- conservent leur liberté de parole à titre individuel,
- peuvent exprimer leur désaccords sur des avis, qui sont enregistrés,
- peuvent communiquer au nom du conseil *selon des modalités définies pour chacun des avis*,
- s'engagent à se déporter s'ils estiment avoir des liens d'intérêts qui seraient de nature à influencer ou à paraître influencer l'exercice indépendant, impartial et objectif de leur fonction.
- sont à l'écoute des autres experts, ouverts au dialogue, et à la co-construction,
- sont disponibles pour les réunions mais aussi pour préparer et mobiliser leurs réseaux pour obtenir les données et informations nécessaires.

Signatures

Brigitte AUTRAN, Présidente, Immunologiste

DocuSigned by:

 452E39DA22A240D...

Thierry LEFRANCOIS, Vétérinaire, One Health

Yvanie CAILLE, Association de patients

DocuSigned by:

 623D31AE2C24A65...

Julie CONTENTI, Urgentiste

DocuSigned by:

 20F0900C186714...

Bruno LINA, Virologue

DocuSigned by:

 17CA278A3956A6...

Fabrice CARRAT, Epidémiologiste

DocuSigned by:

 1A1F9A2A00405...

Simon CAUCHEMEZ, Modélisateur

DocuSigned by:

 60438B4A5E04CF...

Annabel DESGREES du LOU, Démographe

DocuSigned by:

 91CE16282684EC...

Didier FONTENILLE, Entomologiste

DocuSigned by:
Didier FONTENILLE
11E7F3AC4AAA471...

Patrick GIRAUDOUX, Eco-épidémiologiste, One Health

DocuSigned by:
Patrick GIRAUDOUX
8C23DA981F246F...

Mélanie HEARD, Politiste en santé

DocuSigned by:
Mélanie HEARD
F9E73EAA086M30...

Roger LE GRAND, Vaccins, One Health

DocuSigned by:
Roger LE GRAND
0881127D110428...

Céline OFFERLE, Association de patients

DocuSigned by:
Céline OFFERLE
C1F24F08E10742B...

Rémy SLAMA, Epidémiologiste

DocuSigned by:
Rémy SLAMA
E77373CA48E7F48C...

Xavier LESCURE, Infectiologue

DocuSigned by:
Xavier LESCURE
41388F08E04F2...

Denis MALVY, Infectiologue

DocuSigned by:
Denis MALVY
8170871023F427...

Xavier de LAMBALLERIE, Virologue

DocuSigned by:
Xavier de LAMBALLERIE
6BAA5A871C3A423...

Véronique LOYER, Représentante des citoyens

DocuSigned by:
Véronique LOYER
78D9F81A5A104CA...

Olivier SAINT-LARY, Généraliste

DocuSigned by:
Olivier SAINT-LARY
A2B3ABAA479E44A...

Nicoletta MARCHITELLI, Assistante

Nicoletta MARCHITELLI

* groupes d'expertise de l'anses <https://www.anses.fr/fr/content/avis-et-rapports-d-expertise-santé-environnement>:
Biotechnologie ; Eaux ; Perturbateurs endocriniens. Évaluation des risques chimiques liés aux articles et produits de consommation, aux agents physiques et aux nouvelles technologies (climat inclus ds agents physiques), aux milieux aériens

** Organismes entrant dans la composition d'AVIESAN et susceptibles d'interagir avec le Comité : CEA, RESEAU CHU, CNRS, France UNIVERSITES, INRAE, INRIA, INSERM, INSTITUT PASTEUR, IRD, ARIIS, CDEFI, CRAD, EFS, FONDATION MERIEUX, INERIS, INSTITUT CURIE, INSTITUT MINES TELECOM, IRBA, IRSI, UNICANCER

Appendix 5: Editorial in Médecine/Science - "COVARS' mission: how to anticipate health risks in a 'One Health' vision of the exposome".

médecine/sciences 2024 ; 40 : 485-6

Éditorial

La mission du COVARS : comment anticiper les risques sanitaires dans une vision « Une seule Santé » de l'exposome

Brigitte Autran, Thierry Lefrancois, Bruno Lina et les membres du Comité de Veille et d'Anticipation des Risques Sanitaires (COVARS)

» Aujourd'hui, nul ne peut occulter la multiplicité des risques pour la santé humaine. La veille et l'anticipation des risques sanitaires nécessitent d'être considérées dans le cadre d'expositions multiples sous le prisme de l'approche dite « Une seule Santé » ou « One Health » [1]. En effet, les menaces, dont la majorité ne connaît pas de frontières, sont non seulement infectieuses mais aussi liées à divers polluants chimiques et physiques et autres facteurs environnementaux, tels que le réchauffement climatique et la perte de biodiversité. L'origine zoonotique de la plupart des risques infectieux émergents et l'impact de cet « exposome » sur les écosystèmes que constituent les humains, les animaux, les végétaux et autres organismes ne font que souligner cette interdépendance. Ces risques engendrant des coûts humains, sociétaux et économiques considérables nécessitent une anticipation, une prévention et une préparation permanentes. Les activités de surveillance et de veille sanitaire tant en santé humaine qu'animale sont placées sous la responsabilité d'organismes nationaux et supra-nationaux. Une veille scientifique élargie doit impérativement compléter afin d'identifier les déterminants des émergences et en caractériser les mécanismes physiopathologiques et les conséquences pour la santé. Anticiper ces risques s'avère fondamental pour en prévenir ou en limiter les impacts, et, dans tous les cas, pour préparer efficacement la société. Tirant les leçons de la pandémie de Covid-19, le gouvernement français a créé le Comité de veille et d'anticipation des risques sanitaires (COVARS), consultatif, pérenne et indépendant, placé auprès des Ministres de l'enseignement supérieur et de la recherche, de la santé et de la prévention [2]. Son large périmètre de missions, s'inscrivant résolument dans le contexte « Une seule santé » [3] à l'aune de multiples risques sanitaires auxquels sont confrontés la France et le monde impose une vision large, multidisciplinaire, reflétée par la composition du COVARS : épidémiologistes des maladies infectieuses, des pollutions, éco-épidémiologistes, cliniciens infectiologues ou de premier recours, microbiologistes humains et vétérinaires, entomologistes, écologues, immunologistes spécialistes de vaccins, spécialistes en sciences humaines et sociales, ainsi que plusieurs représentants de la démocratie sanitaire. Quels risques sanitaires prendre en considération ? Ceux-ci dépendent du potentiel de nuisance du danger, de l'exposition et de la vulnérabilité de la population, de la capacité de la société à mettre en œuvre une réponse efficace et acceptable, et de la conjonction de facteurs – souvent mal connus – susceptibles d'influencer l'occurrence et le niveau de menace. Pour les analyser, le COVARS travaille en lien étroit avec les organismes chargés de la veille sanitaire et environnementale et les organismes de recherche. Le Comité a rapidement rendu des avis sur la Covid-19, l'épidémie de mPax (variole du singe), les maladies à transmission vectorielle, au premier plan desquelles la dengue et l'infection par le virus West-Nile, ou encore sur les risques pandémiques d'origine zoonotique, comme la grippe aviaire [4]. L'anticipation des risques se décompose, pour le COVARS, en plusieurs séquences dans lesquelles rigueur scientifique, innovation et recherche doivent être omni-

présentes afin de fournir aux décideurs publics des bases robustes sur lesquelles fonder les futures politiques publiques de surveillance, d'alerte et de préparation :

- Une analyse prospective réalisée à partir des données nationales et internationales de veille sanitaire et environnementale et des données scientifiques disponibles. Ainsi le COVARS, répondant à une saisine gouvernementale, a analysé les principaux risques infectieux et environnementaux susceptibles d'induire des situations sanitaires exceptionnelles majeures en France métropolitaine et ultramarine dans les cinq prochaines années [4]. L'analyse de risques a porté sur 35 maladies infectieuses et sur les facteurs environnementaux (climat, perte de biodiversité et pollutions). Le message innovant en est la nécessité d'intégrer à tous les niveaux de la veille et de la préparation, risques infectieux et environnementaux, tant ces derniers influent sur les risques d'occurrence, sur la sévérité des risques infectieux et sur la vulnérabilité des populations.
- Un continuum veille – surveillance – recherche, visant à renforcer, mieux organiser et interconnecter l'évaluation et la surveillance des dangers pouvant affecter l'homme et ses écosystèmes, dans une approche « Une seule santé », et selon des méthodes analytiques les plus modernes et validées. Cette surveillance nécessite une interface étroite avec la recherche scientifique et l'innovation technologique dans de nombreuses disciplines afin de combler les manques de connaissance, développer des outils de diagnostic et de surveillance performants et interconnectés, et définir au mieux de possibles seuils de risque.
- La prévention et la préparation de la réponse : le COVARS recommande une vision holistique impliquant, au-delà de l'établissement de stocks (équipements de sécurité et de prévention, médicaments et vaccins adaptés et validés), une forte dimension d'innovation et de recherche. Tous les aspects de la recherche doivent y être intégrés, depuis une recherche fondamentale totalement générique jusqu'à une recherche très ciblée. Ainsi les succès des vaccins à ARN-messagers (ARNm) anti-Covid-19 n'auraient pas été possibles sans les 50 années de recherche fondamentale sur les ARNm et sur les caractéristiques des Coronavirus. À une étape plus translationnelle, ces recherches doivent inclure des études épidémiologiques rigoureuses sur de grandes cohortes humaines et animales, mais aussi des études utilisant les approches modernes d'analyse d'acides nucléiques « environnementaux » ou dans les eaux usées, l'interconnexion de ces différentes sources de données et la vision d'exposition multiple permettant d'accroître la

production de connaissances. Les études des relations « hôte-pathogène » par classe de pathogènes les plus à risques sont un préliminaire nécessaire au développement de vaccins et de médicaments anti-infectieux adaptés et à l'identification de groupes de personnes à risque. Le soutien au développement d'innovations thérapeutiques ou préventives est clé pour réduire l'impact des crises sanitaires. Ainsi le COVARS, répondant à une saisine gouvernementale sur le futur des vaccins à ARNm, a insisté sur l'immense retard français et la nécessité absolue d'implanter fortement en France ce nouvel écosystème technologique et de recherche aux nombreuses applications préventives et thérapeutiques. De même, cette préparation doit soutenir le développement de thérapies innovantes, telles que les anticorps monoclonaux, pour lesquels le savoir-faire existe en France mais dont le développement n'a pu être mobilisé assez rapidement lors de la pandémie de Covid-19.

– Une réponse rapide grâce à une simplification de la recherche : La complexité administrative de la recherche médicale française est un frein majeur à la capacité du pays à répondre aussi rapidement que nombre de nos voisins. Face à des maladies émergentes dont la sévérité varie selon les facteurs de risque, une recherche clinique ambulatoire doit pouvoir être réalisée de façon aussi rigoureuse que dans les centres hospitalo-universitaires. Le développement anticipé de protocoles cliniques *mock-up* facilement adaptables doit également permettre de tester rapidement des thérapies adaptées.

– La préparation et la participation de la société : les plus belles innovations vaccinales, thérapeutiques, voire numériques, resteront lettre morte sans une appropriation par la société. Cela nécessite une meilleure compréhension des relations science-société en évaluant l'acceptabilité de ces innovations et l'appropriation par la société d'informations solides et rigoureuses afin d'améliorer la littératie en santé. Il faut expliquer la nécessité de l'interconnexion et du partage de données, la stratégie du « tester, tracer, isoler », les campagnes de vaccination de masse ou de prévention des maladies transmises par les insectes. Ces recherches, indispensables aux futures décisions éclairées de politiques publiques, doivent impliquer les communautés, en étant notamment participatives, et être conçues aux niveaux territorial et national tant la réponse des populations peut ne pas être univoque. L'éducation aux risques sanitaires et à leur prévention, à la rigueur et à la compréhension de la démarche scientifique doit impliquer, outre les populations, les décideurs eux-mêmes et est un élément clé de l'anticipation à long terme de ces risques.

– Une dimension internationale de l'anticipation des risques sanitaires : toutes ces étapes de veille et d'anticipation doivent être conçues en lien avec l'Europe et l'international. Cette dimension est nécessaire à la définition de critères communs d'alerte et pour soutenir financièrement les efforts indispensables de recherche et développement qui doivent être conçus comme des investissements pour l'avenir et non comme des dépenses hasardeuses. Les capacités des agences nationales de veille sanitaire à intégrer les signaux d'alerte venant de l'étranger doivent être renforcées. L'agence européenne HERA*, créée lors de la pandémie de Covid-19 devrait voir ses missions élargies. Enfin, il est indispensable que des accords internationaux établissent de véritables programmes équitables et solidaires de préparation aux pandémies.

En conclusion, l'anticipation des risques sanitaires repose sur le concept « Une seule santé » et doit intégrer risques infectieux et environnementaux depuis la veille sanitaire et scientifique jusqu'aux étapes de prospective et de préparation. La dimension de recherche est un élément clé de l'anticipation et de la préparation et doit être multi-disciplinaire. Elle doit être facilitée en temps de crise, tout en préservant

une démarche scientifique rigoureuse et éthique, et inclure les sciences humaines et sociales pour une meilleure compréhension de ces risques et l'acceptation des innovations et des mesures de prévention par la société. L'anticipation des risques suppose pour ce faire d'établir des collaborations fonctionnelles étroites entre les parties prenantes des santés humaine, animale, végétale et des écosystèmes. ♦

The mission of COVARS: how to anticipate health risks within a "One Health" vision of the exposome

LIENS D'INTÉRÊT

Les auteurs déclarent n'avoir aucun lien d'intérêt concernant les données publiées dans cet article.

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Appendix 6: Commentary in Nature communication on Covars' One Health approach (available [here](#))

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One Health approach at the heart of the French Committee for monitoring and anticipating health risks

Thierry Lefrançois, Bruno Lina, COVARS & Brigitte Autran

 Check for updates

The French Committee for Monitoring and Anticipating Health Risks (COVARS) has been strengthening the One Health approach through its interdisciplinary and multi-sectoral composition, the emerging risks it addresses (Covid-19, Mpox, vector-borne diseases, avian influenza...), its holistic approach to risks and its position at the science-decision interface.

The COVID-19 pandemic demonstrated the need for a holistic health approach to anticipate, prepare, and manage health crises. In France, the COVID-19 scientific council, set up in March 2020, produced a prospective report^{1,2} on the lessons of the pandemic and the need for a One Health approach as defined by the One Health High-Level Expert Panel (OHHLEP) and the quadripartite (WHO, WOA, FAO, and UNEP)^{3,4}.

Accordingly, the French government decided, at the end of the state of health emergency in July 2022, to replace the scientific council by a *Committee for Monitoring and Anticipating Health Risks* (COVARS) under the auspices of both the health ministry and the higher education and research ministry. The main objectives were (i) to maintain an independent and transparent multidisciplinary scientific advisory committee in charge of providing the government with evidence-based recommendations on health risks, (ii) to have an integrated approach to health and therefore to include risks related to the environment and climate change, beyond infectious diseases, and (iii) to anticipate potential health crises in order to promote prevention and preparedness. The ministries clearly stated in their press release that a One Health approach was fully included in the COVARS missions⁵.

Here, we illustrate how this interdisciplinary and multi-sectoral committee at the interface between science and decision-making has contributed to enhancing and improving the understanding and implementation of the One Health approach in France. This is highlighted through the operational functioning of the committee and the content of its reports on several specific risks (COVID-19, Mpox, vector-borne diseases, highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI)).

One Health in the multidisciplinary and multisectoral composition of the committee

The One Health approach was reflected in its multidisciplinary composition that includes 16 experts with field experience in human, animal, or environmental health sectors in different disciplines (epidemiology, modeling, virology, infectiology, general medicine and emergency, veterinary epidemiology and microbiology, entomology, ecology, immunology and vaccinology, sociology, population science,

health policy, etc.). The full list of members with their disciplines is indicated in each published advice⁶. Importantly, several experts had a longstanding experience with One Health approaches to emerging, vector-borne, or environmental diseases.

In addition, three civil society representatives (patients' associations and citizens' representatives) provide an important non-expert opinion to the group. Their contributions complement the scientific expertise with experience and knowledge of health democracy, community health approaches, field management of emerging diseases, and of the most vulnerable groups. They participate in the early stages of the process to ensure that recommendations are balanced with real-life experiences and testimonies of relevant professions or charities. They participate in the evaluation of acceptability of COVARS recommendations by the civil society and of their sustainability.

The committee consults with many stakeholders from different sectors, including national and regional agencies and research organizations involved in human and veterinary surveillance, patient associations, breeder associations, non-governmental organizations, diagnostic and vaccine developers, and ministries.

Altogether, the COVARS build a broad and integrated view on each subject aligned with the new inclusive definition and characterization of One Health^{3,4}.

One Health in the priority risks

The COVARS responds to the French government's requests or can seize itself of health risks identified as priorities. These are defined during specific seminars, updated regularly according to the sanitary situation, and discussed with the ministries. In its first year of operation, the COVARS published 10 reports or recommendations⁶:

- Seven, in direct response to Government requests (COVID-19, Mpox, and mRNA vaccines)
- Two, produced following an initial specific request on Dengue that the COVARS discussed and reformulated with the Ministries. COVARS first produced a general report on vector-borne diseases, followed by two more specific reports on Dengue, Zika, Chikungunya (*Aedes* sp. being the vector), and on West Nile and Usutu (*Culex* sp. being the vector)
- One, is entirely self-referred (HPAI). Several factors make HPAI a particularly significant One Health risk. First, it cannot be eradicated because of the immensity and diversity of its wildlife and domestic reservoirs. Second, the rapid transmission between birds and its severity in wild birds increases the risk of transmission to and between mammals, and ultimately to humans. Third, climate change is altering the migratory patterns of wild birds and possibly their resistance to viruses, thus favoring the emergence of new HPAI outbreaks.

The work on vector-borne diseases and HPAI shows how COVARS can prioritize complex and multi-sectoral issues based on its own expertise.

One Health in the holistic analysis of the risks

One Health recommendations as specific parts of some recommendations. In the Covid-19 report, COVARS recommended to monitor the circulation of variants in animals and assess the risks of reverse zoonosis through immune escape or recombination induced by circulation in animal species (mink, deer, and hamsters), which can be enhanced by intensive virus circulation in areas with close interaction between humans and wild animals (e.g. live markets in China).

Similarly, the Mpox report analyzed the risk of animal-to-human transmission, either in natural habitats with susceptible species (squirrels, marmots) having sporadic contact with humans, or in anthropic contexts with animals of unknown sensitivity being in close contact with humans (dormouse, pet rats, and mice, dogs, or zoo animals). The COVARS recommended monitoring infection in animals and not only in humans and suggested that eradication in Europe would be difficult if an animal reservoir was detected.

The report on the future of mRNA vaccines analyzed veterinary vaccines in development (avian influenza) and suggested the need to coordinate research and development processes between the animal and human sectors.

One Health at the heart of the COVARS work and recommendation.

The vector-borne diseases reports highlighted the need to develop a One Health approach for transmission studies, human and animal disease surveillance, vector surveillance and control, epidemiological analysis and modeling, and also to consider climate change and socioeconomic factors in risk assessment. The COVARS recommended a coordinated inter-ministerial and multi-sectoral commitment to the surveillance and control of vector-borne diseases and an evaluation of the effectiveness of vector control techniques and their impact on the environment and on human health.

Regarding HPAI, the COVARS recommended to reinforce and coordinate multidisciplinary and multi-sectoral measures aimed at tackling this risk: First, rapidly implement the poultry vaccination strategy based on the DIVA strategy (differentiating infected from vaccinated animals) as recommended by Anses and extend the recommendation of seasonal influenza vaccination to people at risk in contact with birds. Second, adapt prevention and farm management counter-measures by actively seeking alternatives to preventive slaughtering, by improving euthanasia conditions of farm animals, and by developing support programs for affected farmers. Third, expand and strengthen human and financial resources to intensify domestic and wild animal, human, and environmental surveillance. Fourth, facilitate the collaboration between veterinary and human medicine, and allow human respiratory samples to be collected either by self-sampling or by veterinarians with diagnosis to be carried out in the veterinary laboratories. Last, create a multi-disciplinary emergency unit that can be activated rapidly in the event of a crisis.

One Health in the science-decision and science-society interactions

The COVARS also operates in close interaction with other ministries (agriculture, ecological transition, foreign affairs, and overseas territories) all being essential for a One Health inter-ministerial approach. More specifically, the COVARS interacts with the technical directorates

of these ministries but also with the cabinets and the Ministers themselves under the prime Minister cabinet umbrella.

The COVARS has also established strong links with human and animal health agencies, with their expert groups, and with the main research organizations involved in One Health. Auditions of specialized expert groups or research teams feed its recommendations and conversely, its reports can recommend to set up new expert groups or research work.

These regular meetings with ministries, agencies, and research organizations foster nationwide collaborations. Such close interactions between experts and decision-makers also contribute to the appropriation of the One Health concept, and favor its practical implementation at the national level. It also helps to follow the actual impact of the COVARS recommendations.

The COVARS recommendations are published on the ministry's websites, and disseminated through press conferences, TV or radio interviews, or in the written press, all contributing to the dissemination of the One Health concept in society and to the literacy of the population on this matter. This is to be pursued through participatory research, communication, and youth education.

The current composition of the committee already promotes bridges with the civil society and the inclusion of a social psychologist in addition to the population scientist should help foster empowerment and general population engagement.

Discussion and perspectives

Much remains to be done to strengthen efficient and transparent interactions between scientists, stakeholders, citizens, and decision-makers on One Health issues, and to improve inter-ministerial cooperation, concrete actions, and societal engagement on the issue.

Several COVARS reports have identified general weaknesses in policy responses that should be addressed: administrative issues for One Health research and implementation, lack of long-term research funding, lack of links between health databases from different sources, work in silos, weakness of social sciences and primary care research on emerging diseases, difficulties in evaluating multidisciplinary researches, weak links between research and surveillance.

Given the growing evidence of the interrelations between emerging diseases and climate change², and/or biodiversity loss³, the COVARS will address health, climate change, and biodiversity crises altogether. It recommends not only to promote this global and complex approach within research and surveillance, but also, for a long-term impact, to train health professionals and decision-makers, and enhance public education.

Obviously, the COVARS is not the only structure implementing or favoring One Health in France. Ministries, research organizations, health agencies, civil society, or regions are key to strengthen this approach.

Other countries have also recently strengthened the framework for implementing One Health. In the USA, a new office for pandemic preparedness and response has been established, with a broad integrated approach, and a One Health bill to prevent, detect, and respond to biological threats was introduced in late 2022. Senegal has chosen to appoint a One Health advisor to the government. Altogether, the national implementation of One Health is still very heterogeneous in terms of structure and impact, yet.

Promoting inter-sectoral collaboration at the territorial level to better monitor emerging diseases is also critical. In addition, bringing together all the stakeholders and the public at this scale should help

defining a healthy territory, how to monitor it, and the measures to be implemented to maintain it harmoniously.

Scaling up at the international level is also essential. We need to build on and strengthen existing regional One Health networks, involving all countries with the same regional epidemiological characteristics and emerging risks, regardless of their resources.

The COVARS aims at interacting more with similar structures in Europe to establish guidelines for such committees⁹ by sharing recommendations, discuss on transboundary health issues, and favor interactions with international initiatives tackling pandemic risk like Prezode¹⁰. National and regional One Health strategies should be supported by the quadripartite, which can provide guidance for better implementation of One Health at the global level (One Health Joint Plan of Action¹¹).

Efficient implementation of One Health interventions requires a methodology based on multisectoral and multidisciplinary collaborations, joint active participation and cooperation, shared investments and resources, planning, and monitoring to allow evaluation of the social and economic benefits of this approach¹². The COVARS is currently working with the French ministries to implement a monitoring and evaluation strategy of its recommendations.

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Author contributions

T.L. conceived the paper. T.L., B.L., and B.A. wrote and prepared the paper. All the other authors, members of the COVARS consortium read, made corrections, and improved the paper through specific additions.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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Comment

COVARS

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Appendix 7: Tasks assigned to COVARS human resources

<p>Project Manager</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Drafting of notices, notes and reports ○ Documentary research to support plenary meetings and the drafting of opinions (documents of various kinds: scientific, legal, journalistic, administrative, etc.). ○ Occasional international benchmarking on a subject of interest, and scientific and legal monitoring. ○ PowerPoint presentation to support the presentation of COVARS' opinions to the authorities ○ Translation of executive summaries and notices into English
<p>Communication officer</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Organization of press conferences when COVARS notices are published ○ Contact with various COVARS journalists to promote its opinions and notes in the press ○ Mission to disseminate opinions to the general public and analyse the key messages for each opinion ○ Media monitoring of media appearances by COVARS or its members ○ Health and research news watch for COVARS members ○ Communications strategy and consulting services for the press and general public ○ Writing press releases ○ Creation of a COVARS graphic identity ○ LinkedIn creation and management ○ Liaison with communications departments of ministerial offices, health agencies and research institutes
<p>Assistant</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Organization of COVARS hearings: contacts with agencies, ministerial departments, researchers ○ Organization of quarterly COVARS seminars ○ Administrative support ○ Formatting of notices, notes and Powerpoint presentations

Appendix 8: Summary of COVARS' main recommendations

Table 8-1: Main health recommendations by major

ACUTE RESPIRATORY INFECTIONS (INCLUDING COVID-19)	PREVENT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Facilitate and accelerate vaccination campaigns throughout France, including overseas territories - Encourage barrier gestures (mask use) to protect the most vulnerable and limit the burden on hospitals - Improve indoor air quality and widespread use of CO2 sensors in schools
	MONITOR and DETECT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Continue to promote screening (antigen tests and self-tests), - Continue to monitor wastewater, - Undertake research into the coordination of screening methods and databases to strengthen surveillance.
	TREAT	Amplify the use of Paxlovid with conditional prescriptions
	INVOLVING SOCIETY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promote a culture of empowerment for prevention - Involve and consult health democracy bodies (notably the National and Regional Health Conferences) to ensure long-term, nationwide anti-Covid-19 control strategies (in France and the French overseas territories).
MONKEYPOX	PREVENT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Continue to provide information to the most vulnerable segments of the population to reduce risk-taking behaviour and facilitate diagnosis and rapid access to care, with the help of associations. - Achieve herd immunity through full vaccination (at least two doses) of the target population, involving sexual health centres and other health professionals. - Consider extending vaccination to people at risk of STIs - Build national stockpiles or national production capacity for MVA-BN vaccines
	WATCH AND DIAGNOSE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integrate the Mpox virus into STI surveillance - Offer screening to anyone with a history of STIs - Strengthen diagnostic surveillance and sequencing capacity by relaxing MOT regulations for the Monkeypox virus, while complying with safety regulations.
	SEARCH	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evaluate the value of wider access to anti-viral treatment with tecovirimat to reduce viral replication - Pursue the study of the natural history of the infection through longitudinal cohort studies within a national and international framework.
VECTOR-BORNE DISEASES/ ARBOVIROSES	OBSERVE AND DETECT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Redefine the "signalement moustique" website, enable it to detect the presence and density of mosquitoes, and connect it to a European site. - Improve the SI-LAV (Système d'Information pour la prévention des maladies vectorielles) application, enabling ARS and mosquito control operators to enter information in the field.
	PREVENTING AND MOBILIZING	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improving preparation and information, particularly in "emerging" territories (e.g. France) training for local authorities and healthcare professionals - Facilitate the interconnection of operators (EFS, ABM) to an updated SPF surveillance database to prevent transmission by blood, organ or tissue donation, and prepare the current system in mainland France for a probable increase in cases.

VECTOR-BORNE DISEASES/ ARBOVIROSES		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Raise public awareness of appropriate behaviour to combat vector proliferation - Suggest alternatives to biocides: traps, repellents, mosquito nets, TIS (sterile insect technique)
	INNOVATE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Support technological advances in diagnosis and surveillance, with complete and rapid sequencing of identified viruses, and ensure that West Nile virus screening remains adapted to a rapidly evolving epidemiological context. - Develop specific anti-viral therapeutic strategies and make hyper-immune immunoglobulins available in the event of severe infection or to at-risk patients. - Support vaccine research, - Accelerate information and care for people at risk of severe forms of the disease (sickle cell disease, pregnant women).
	MANAGING AND GOVERNING	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clarify and optimize the roles of the public players involved in LAV by creating a national inter-professional technical centre (CTI) at regional or departmental level; - Resizing the ORSEC plan - Renovate the 2016 CNEV "Guide à l'attention des collectivités souhaitant mettre en oeuvre une lutte contre les moustiques urbains vecteurs de dengue, chikungunya et de zika", enriched with Culex, West Nile and Usutu aspects, and distribute widely.
	EVALUATE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop indicators of entomological and epidemiological effectiveness and of the ecological and societal impact of actions - Evaluate and publish the effectiveness of different insecticide treatments and interventions
HPAI	WATCH	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Intensify and coordinate human, animal and environmental surveillance - Reinforce surveillance and sequencing of influenza viruses; anticipate active surveillance of cattle and goat farms close to contaminated bird farms; special vigilance for dairy products
	PREVENT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adapt preventive and management measures for avian outbreaks, in particular by improving euthanasia conditions and seeking alternatives to sheltering birds and preventive culling.
	VACCINATE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Animal vaccination : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implement DIVA strategies for future vaccines. - Evaluate alternatives to preventive slaughter by reactive ring vaccination or by checking the immunity of vaccinated animals, and support research aimed at improving early vaccine immunity. - Human vaccination: Support seasonal influenza vaccination of exposed personnel (healthcare professionals, veterinarians, livestock farmers) and reduce the costs borne by professionals.
	SENSITIZE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reinforce hygiene and biosafety training for farmers and operators (DGAL) - Reinforce and facilitate the application of biosafety measures when transporting animals. - Raise public and medical awareness of avian risks
	COORDINATE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strengthen veterinary/human medicine collaboration in infected farms - Open a multi-stakeholder discussion on the economic and health impact of intensive poultry farming, in anticipation of the effects of climate change.- Alert European authorities to farming practices that encourage viruses to evolve and spread to mammals.
	TRAINING AND COMMUNICATION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strengthen and harmonize training and information for human and animal health professionals on the risks of HPAI and the clinical signs of the disease. - Conduct targeted communication and participatory monitoring

		campaigns , particularly in high-risk areas and for people at risk, in times of crisis and between crises.
		-
RISKS FROM EXCEPTIONAL HEALTH SITUATIONS MAJOR	INTEGRATE	- Integrate environmental factors into health risk preparedness (infectious and non-infectious) , in particular climate change, pollution and the biodiversity crisis
	PREPARE	- Organise collective support for the response and combating infodemia - Prepare the development of non-pharmaceutical and pharmaceutical diagnostic and countermeasure capabilities through research
	COORDINATE	- Strengthen international coordination of preparedness and response to health crises - Develop indicators to support risk monitoring and reduction policies and understand vulnerabilities
CHOLERA IN MAYOTTE	WATCH	Strengthen wastewater monitoring in conjunction with the SUM'eau system
	MANAGE	- Open up access to water - Increase the number of healthcare staff involved in "Going Towards", in partnership with local associations and NGOs.

Table 8-2: Cross-cutting research and monitoring recommendations across all COVARS advices and notes

SURVEILLANCE	
Decompartamentalizing and strengthening monitoring, diagnosis and management at the animal/human interface	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Draw up an assessment of human and animal surveillance systems in France and overseas, and propose coordinated organizations (human - veterinary - entomological - environmental) based on integrated objectives for the development of clear protocols. • Decompartamentalize surveillance, diagnosis and management at the animal/human interface by creating networks of local and national players. • Support and strengthen national and international surveillance systems, to facilitate data feedback, matching and sharing, as well as scalability in times of crisis. • Support innovative approaches to monitoring and capturing data useful for monitoring and research (innovative monitoring designs, social networks, mobility data, wastewater, new microbiological approaches, use of AI...). • Rationalize and formalize vector control monitoring, and develop a single, verified, accessible information system aggregating human, animal and environmental data. • Develop and organize active animal surveillance, particularly in equine and avian species, and explore the various animal compartments in which viruses are maintained and spread. • Set up surveillance of viral circulation in the entomological compartment, initiated in the form of collaboration between surveillance and research. • Strengthening surveillance resources : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ passive wildlife (SAGIR network); clarify responsibilities of the OFB and the DDPP. ○ and integrate it in a sustainable way
Strengthen national watch and international One Health and Exposome	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set up a high-level expertise structure to support the integration of human, animal and environmental data, under the aegis of the Ministries of Health and Research. • Create a modern information system within Santé Publique France, integrating national and international human and environmental data, backed up by a SpF department dedicated to the international surveillance of vector-borne and infectious diseases, to facilitate measures to reduce the risk of transfusion.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthen international One Health and Exposome health monitoring of major health risks, particularly at SpF, in conjunction with the ECDC, the national animal health epidemiological monitoring platform (PNESA) and animal and human health research organizations, to ensure strong interaction between monitoring and research, • Propose a European framework for the co-production of indicators to support risk reduction and monitoring policies, and gain a better understanding of climate-related areas of vulnerability at the interface between man, animals and the environment.
<p>Promote real coordination between national, regional and international players</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organize concerted action by national and regional players (monitoring, control, research) who have proven their effectiveness, and make them the "laboratory" for transferring operational research activities to integrated monitoring. • Adapt monitoring protocols to the territory in question, particularly for overseas territories • Establish active collaboration between medical and veterinary health authorities. Encourage participatory surveillance initiatives for interactions between wild and farmed animals (e.g. birds for avian influenza, etc.), • On an international scale, increase European and international information sharing and the interconnection of surveillance networks (including WHO/OMSA), and define criteria for severity and probability of emergence on this scale.
<p>Making MOT regulations more flexible</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Align with the international situation and improve the responsiveness of surveillance and the competitiveness of French research by significantly relaxing the rules governing the possession, use and transport of nucleic acids, in order to : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rapidly organize and participate in national, European and international external quality controls, - Facilitating the creation of biobanks, viral genomics by sequencing - Improving the management and evaluation of serum-neutralization vaccination protocols - Enable wastewater-based molecular epidemiological surveillance and environmental research
<p>Anticipate the information system to be deployed in health crisis situations interface care-surveillance-research</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Map foreseeable healthcare data needs in crisis situations, in conjunction with all the players involved. • Improve coordination between SpF and ARS for more fluid and efficient data collection in crisis situations • Provide human, logistical and IT resources in inter-crisis situations to strengthen partnerships between health agencies, research teams and reference centers, in order to improve capacity for production and analysis of human and animal health data, surveillance and modeling to prepare against emergencies, • Provide the capacity rapid and effective mobilization in the event of a crisis, notably through specific regulatory frameworks and derogation processes for the reuse of healthcare data and facilitated access to healthcare data for researchers, as well as through rapid funding and deployment mechanisms for research that complements surveillance. • Evaluate the systems put in place by carrying out health crisis scenario tests in conjunction with experts in the relevant fields
<p>Involving citizens in the decision-making process concerning health data</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involve citizens in health data production and governance processes, integrating the specific characteristics of overseas territories at every stage. • Improve effective consent and information procedures for the re-use of health data in health crisis situations. • Transparent communication: Clearly inform the public about the potential benefits (and risks) of health data sharing, particularly in terms of research and public decision-making, and encourage feedback from citizens. • Facilitate the possibility of opting out or objecting via, for example, a centralized portal, and engage in ongoing dialogue to address citizens' concerns in order to improve processes.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set up a company-wide ethical debate on IS developments, interoperability and accessibility, with a long-term vision that includes the development of the European Health Data Area.
RESEARCH	
<p>Improving the responsiveness of French research in times of crisis and between crises</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintain "flash funds" for the immediate initiation of research in the event of a crisis • Support multi-year financing programs • Integrate research into all stages of a health crisis, including prevention, preparation and management • Ensure continuity of funding between crises on given topics
<p>Interconnecting, structuring and strengthening access to healthcare data</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthen researchers' access to integrated health surveillance and research databases, and streamline administrative and regulatory frameworks • Coordinate the various players involved in the production and use of healthcare data • Bring citizens closer to the issue of open health data and develop open science policy • Develop the ability to match databases (using a unique identifier such as the NIR) • Enhance healthcare data, in particular by structuring the network of healthcare data warehouses, especially hospital data warehouses, standardizing the repositories used, integrating environmental data, and setting up human and material resources. • Improve the updating of healthcare data through a just-in-time PMSI data feedback system, such as PMSI fast-track.
<p>Promoting interdisciplinary research between the humanities, social sciences and health sciences</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support interdisciplinary research between the humanities, social sciences and health sciences, to strengthen the ability of public policy-makers and citizens to understand health risks and implement appropriate measures. • Create or strengthen interdisciplinary research groups in collaboration with human and social sciences, epidemiology, clinical and biomedical research. • Develop intersectoriality in partnership with health agencies, patient associations and research organizations in human, animal and environmental health. • Promote innovative research approaches that facilitate the understanding of complex statistical data involving human, animal and socio-ecosystem health in crisis and inter-crisis contexts.
<p>Strengthening integrated "One Health" approaches</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support an integrated One Health approach in major research areas, and strengthen interdisciplinary groups and integrated approaches to research in human, animal and environmental health. • Support and strengthen ambitious multi-disciplinary and cross-sectoral programs and plan major holistic, cross-sectoral, integrated research projects on health risks due to emerging issues, pollutants, etc. • Coordinate research and development of human and animal vaccines to benefit more rapidly from technological advances • Strengthen European initiatives for an integrated approach to human and animal health, climate, ecotoxicity and biodiversity, including : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Task-Force between European health agencies to strengthen their scientific recommendations in integrated One Health approaches. - DG HERA to open it up to the One Health concept of infectious and environmental risks.
<p>Taking climate and environmental change into account in human health studies</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Objectives for 2030: i) pathogen and host evolution mechanisms, effects of anthropogenic changes on pathogen emergence; ii) links between socio-ecosystems and chronic non-infectious diseases; iii) long-term monitoring of population health by facilitating access to large databases and tools for data management, analysis, modeling and interpretation.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Periodically reassess knowledge of pesticide-related health risks and human-animal transmission cycles within the ecosystem, in order to guide public action towards better protection of populations. • Regularly assess the impact of climate change and the biodiversity crisis on vector-borne diseases and vectors • Seizing the opportunity offered by the Program Agencies to strengthen health and environmental research programs
<p>Strengthening research in overseas France</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthen research in the French overseas territories, in particular to gain a better understanding of epidemiological cycles and pathogen circulation between DROMs, taking account of specific regional features.
<p>Empowering citizens in the face of health risks through research</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop intervention research programs in health crisis situations to inform the decisions of non-specialists, provide citizens with effective, scientifically-based health protection tools, and combat misinformation. • Develop a community of researchers with scientific expertise in strategies and methods for strengthening individual and collective capacities (empowerment) to deal with exceptional health situations. • Develop coordinated research along the lines of the Convergence institutes or the research centres developed in the UK and Germany, focusing on the ability of citizens to protect themselves from health risks and misinformation.

Appendix 9: COVARS institutional and scientific communications

Présentations du COVARS au Parlement	
06/12/2022	Assemblée Nationale (Commission des Affaires Sociales) : Présentation du COVARS
19/06/2023	Sénat : 26ème Journée Nationale d'Étude « Élus Santé Publique et Territoires »
10/04/2024	Sénat : table ronde risques épidémiologiques
Présentations des Avis du COVARS aux institutions sanitaires et de recherche (hors Présentations aux Ministres et RDV réguliers avec DG Agences sanitaires et de recherche)	
25/10/22	ARS Corse Présentation du COVARS et point d'actualité Covid-19
25/11/2022	DGOS : Assemblée Générale : Présentation du COVARS
12/2022	DGS : CASA : Présentation du COVARS
12/2022	RIM (Conseillers PR, PM, Minsistères) : Points d'actualité et suivi Avis COVARS
8/3/2023	SGPI : Présentation du COVARS
03/2023	RIM Points d'actualité et suivi Avis COVARS : IAHP et Arboviroses
09/2023	RIM : Points d'actualité et suivi Avis COVARS : IAHP et Arboviroses
11/2023	RFSA : Présentation du COVARS et aspects One health
01/2024	Séminaires de l'Hôpital Foch : Présentation du COVARS et aspects One health
15/2/2024	DGS : CASA : Présentation du COVARS et Avis
04/2024	DGS : Présentation Avis SSE du COVARS
04/2024	DGOS : Présentation Avis SSE du COVARS
04/2024	RIM : Présentation Avis SSE du COVARS
05/2024	DAEI (MSP) : Présentation Avis SSE du COVARS
21/5/2024	SPF : Présentation Avis SSE du COVARS,
4/7/2024	ANR : Présentation Avis en SHS du COVARS
24/7/2024	AP-HP (DG) : Présentation Avis COVARS sur Bases de Données en Santé
25/7/2024	AIS : Présentation Avis COVARS sur Bases de Données en Santé
Invitations du COVARS: Tables ronde et présentations	
15/11/2022	HERA (EU) : Présentation du COVARS
02/2023	ANR : Présentation du COVARS et des Avis
14/03/2023	CGAER : Présentation du COVARS et aspects One health
30/03/2023	ITMO I3M : Présentation du COVARS et aspects One health
12/06/2023	CMGF : Présentation du COVARS et des Avis
06/2023	EFS : Présentation du COVARS et des Avis
09/2023	Collectif associatif TRT-5 CHV : Présentation du COVARS et travaux sur Bases de données en Santé
10/11/2023	Copil Réseau français de santé animale : Présentation du covars
01/2024	Séminaires de l'Hôpital Foch : Présentation du COVARS et aspects One health
01/07/2024	CCNE : Présentation du COVARS, Avis SSE et aspects One health
04/07/2024	Colloque sante environnement : One health accélérer l'agenda (Pharmaceutique/Be Concerned)
Cours et conférences sur le COVARS	
01/09/2023	International Master of Science in Infectious Diseases and One Health" (IDOH+), Nantes (Erasmus Mundus): interaction science décision en santé
09/10/2024	Ecole nationale des services vétérinaires : Residential course One Health : interaction science décision et One Health
25/10/2024	Société francophone de santé environnement : interaction science décision
13/12/2024	Académie vétérinaire de France : -Covars et one health - "Entre COVARS et Une Seule Santé : veille et anticipation des risques sanitaires"
26/03/2024	ENS Effsciences : cours "Approches One Health : vers une nouvelle gouvernance du vivant ?"
23/04/2024	Assemblée générale du réseau caribéen de santé animale CaribVET : Covars et interaction science décision
11/06/2024	Ecole vétérinaire Unilasalle : cours "interaction science-décision dans le domaine sanitaire One health"

Communications et conférences - Niveau territorial

15/12/2022	Alliance santé biodiversité: Une seule santé et territoire: quels enjeux ? Comment le CoVARS s'est-il emparé du concept une seule santé
13/06/2023	Assemblée générale ARS Bourgogne Franche-Comté
06/10/2023	Rencontres Santé Société Georges Canguilhem, Strasbourg
19/10/2023	CPTS CaPaciTÉS Besançon et Métropole : le CoVARS Quesaco ?
24/11/2023	Réunion annuelle PRSE4 Occitanie (Narbonne) : One Health
03/07/2024	Table ronde chambre régionale des compte – Université de Montpellier : Démoustication

Appendix 10: COVARS media appearances

Table 10 - 1: Main appearances in the trade press, by theme (non-exhaustive)

Nom du Journal	Titre de l’article (Lien hypertexte sur les titres)	Date de parution
Création du COVARS		
Le Point Vétérinaire	Deux vétérinaires intègrent le Covars	6 janvier 2023
Covid-19		
Hospimedia	Le COVARS rejette l’idée d’une gestion banalisée des risques sanitaires saisonniers	24 octobre 2024
Santé magazine	Covid-19 : la présidente du Covars encourage la prescription de Paxlovid	29 novembre 2022
La veille acteurs de santé	Point d’actualité du Comité de Veille et d’Anticipation des Risques Sanitaires sur la Covid-19 et recommandations (Avis)	16 décembre 2022
IRA		
Hospimedia	Le COVARS veut se saisir du sujet de la perception sociétale du risque sanitaire	23 décembre 2022
Futur des vaccins ARNm		
Egora La voix des médecins	L’avenir des vaccins à ARN messenger : le nouvel avis du Covars	16 février 2023
Influenza		
La dépêche vétérinaire	Influenza : le Covars propose d’élargir la vaccination contre la grippe saisonnière, notamment aux vétérinaires	Mercredi 14 juin 2023
Le Quotidien du Médecin	Alerte grippe H5N1 aux États-Unis : le Covars rassure sur le risque pandémique, mais recommande une surveillance renforcée	31 mai 2024
La santé au quotidien	Grippe aviaire : le risque d’une épidémie en France est «réel» selon un virologue	14 juin 2024
La dépêche vétérinaire	Influenza : le Covars recommande de surveiller les élevages bovins près des foyers	5 juin 2024
Agri71.fr	Influenza : le Covars recommande de surveiller les élevages bovins	21 juin 2024
Covid-Long		
Le quotidien du pharmacien	Covid long : une prise en charge insatisfaisante en France	9 novembre 2023
Le Quotidien du Médecin	Covid long : le parcours de soins reste « chaotique », déplore le Covars	8 novembre 2023
Medscape	Syndrome post-COVID : le Covars appelle à créer des structures multidisciplinaires pérennes	16 novembre 2023
Egora	La reconnaissance du Covid long par le Covars, une heureuse surprise face au déni du Gouvernement	19 novembre 2023
Egora	Syndrome post-Covid : une prise en charge défailante	10 novembre 2023

La République des Pyrénées	Covid long : une prise en charge « insatisfaisante » en France, selon le Covars	9 novembre 2023
Sciences et avenir	Covid long : une prise en charge "insatisfaisante" en France, selon le Covars	8 novembre 2023
Nouvel Obs	La prise en charge du Covid long reste « insatisfaisante » en France, affirme le Covars	8 novembre 2023
Midi libre	Covid long : diagnostic difficile, profils les plus touchés, traitement... le point sur les dernières recommandations du Covars	8 novembre 2023
Républicain Lorrain	Isolement, difficultés financières... Le Covid long doit être mieux pris en charge, alerte le Covars	8 novembre 2023
Maladies à transmission vectorielle		
Le Quotidien du médecin	L'inexorable montée des arboviroses	17 février 2023
Destination Santé	Chikungunya, dengue... pourquoi le nombre cas devrait se multiplier	11 avril 2023
Santé magazine	Climat : des flambées de dengue, Zika et chikungunya à prévoir en métropole « au cours des prochains étés »	31 août 2023
Cartographie des risques de situation sanitaire exceptionnelle		
Le quotidien du pharmacien	Rapport du COVARS : Quelles épidémies frapperont la France dans les cinq ans à venir ?	25 avril 2024
Egora – la voix des médecins	Les principaux risques sanitaires dans les 5 prochaines années, listés par le Covars	18 avril 2024
Le Point Vétérinaire	Un nouvel avis du COVARS sur les risques de situations sanitaires exceptionnelles majeures	17 avril 2024
Le Quotidien du Médecin	Zoonoses et arboviroses sont les principaux risques sanitaires à court terme, selon le Covars	10 avril 2024
VIH.org	Cartographie des risques par le Covars : utile ou futile ?	3 juillet 2024
Note Sciences Humaines et Sociales (6 mai 2024)		
Le quotidien du Médecin	Le Covars plaide pour un Institut de recherche chargé de booster la culture de la prévention	7 mai 2024
One Health		
Le quotidien du Médecin	Le Covars pose en modèle son approche « One Health »	1 décembre 2023
La dépêche vétérinaire	One Health : un concept au cœur du Covars	13 décembre 2023
Choléra à Mayotte		
Egora – la voix des médecins	Choléra : la réserve sanitaire mobilisée à Mayotte	8 juillet 2023
Egora – la voix des médecins	Choléra : le Covars s'alarme de la situation	31 mai 2024
Le Quotidien du Médecin	AME, One Health, fake news... Le Covars se positionne à l'approche des législatives	28 juin 2024

Table 10-2: Main COVARS citations in national media, by theme (non-exhaustive)

Nom du Journal	Titre de l'article (Lien hypertexte sur les titres Nom)	Date de parution
Création du COVARS		
TF1 info	Covars : qui compose le nouveau Comité de veille sanitaire, le successeur du Conseil scientifique ?	29 septembre 2022
CNEWS	Covars : qui sont les 18 membres du comité, successeur du conseil scientifique ?	
Le Figaro	Risques sanitaires : le successeur du Conseil scientifique désormais au complet	
L'express	Infectiologue, vétérinaire, virologue... Qui sont les membres du nouveau comité scientifique?	
France Info	Covid-19 : qui sont les 18 membres du comité de veille et d'anticipation des risques sanitaires, qui a succédé au Conseil scientifique ?	
Europe 1	Quatre choses à savoir sur le Covars, le successeur du Conseil scientifique	2 octobre 2022
Covid-19		
Challenges	Coronavirus-La huitième vague en phase ascendante en France-Covars	4 octobre 2022
20 minutes	Covid-19 : une 8e vague « d'intensité modérée », selon le Covars, nouveau conseil scientifique	24 octobre 2022
L'express	Covid-19 : ce qu'il faut retenir du premier avis du Covars, le nouveau comité scientifique	
France Info	Covid-19 : dans son premier avis, le Covars évoque une vague "d'intensité modérée" mais reste prudent pour la suite	25 octobre 2022
Le JDD	Le gouvernement demande au COVARS de se prononcer sur un éventuel retour du masque obligatoire	2 décembre 2022
Capital	Covid-19 : le Covars saisi par le gouvernement en vue d'un retour du masque obligatoire	
Le Point	Covid-19 : le Covars plaide pour un retour en force du masque	4 décembre 2022
RTL	Coronavirus : la présidente du Covars déplore le niveau "désolant" de la vaccination	
France info	Le Covars plaide pour des "encouragements extrêmement forts à renforcer le port du masque" dans les transports et les lieux clos	6 décembre 2022
L'Express	Covid-19, à quoi ressemblera l'hiver ? Quatre experts répondent	11 décembre 2023
France Bleu	Covid-19 : hausse de la circulation du virus, les autorités sanitaires appellent à se faire vacciner	15 décembre 2023
L'opinion	«La Covid sera là tous les hivers, soyons responsables!» exhortent les scientifiques du Covars	19 décembre 2022
Libération	Covid-19 : le Covars appelle au port du masque sans recommander son obligation	
Capital	Covid-19: Le Covars recommande la gratuité des masques dans les lieux où ils sont nécessaires	20 décembre 2022
BFMTV	Covid-19: le Covars recommande le port du masque et la vaccination pour les fêtes de fin d'année	21 décembre 2023
L'opinion	Covid-19 en Chine: «Le dépistage aux frontières n'a jamais empêché un virus de pénétrer», assure la présidente du Covars	
Challenges	Covid-19 : les contrôles aux frontières en France ne sont pas nécessaires à ce stade, selon le Covars	29 décembre 2022
France 24	Sur la piste de l'intrigant Covid long, les chercheurs progressent	
Le JDD	Covid-19 : le Covars désapprouve l'idée d'un retour des contrôles aux frontières « pour l'instant »	
Le Figaro	Covid-19 : le Covars avait proposé de demander un certificat de vaccination aux voyageurs en provenance de Chine	3 janvier 2023

TF1 Info	Covid-19 : le masque obligatoire pas nécessaire "pour l'instant" malgré le regain épidémique, selon le Covars	23 août 2023
Capital	Covid-19 : faut-il craindre un retour brutal de l'épidémie ?	19 avril 2024
IRA		
CNEWS	Triple épidémie : le Covars ne se prononce pas sur l'obligation du masque	
20 minutes	Covid-19, grippe, bronchiolite : Toujours pas d'avis du Covars sur un retour du masque obligatoire	
Le Monde	Covid-19, grippe, bronchiolite... Les scientifiques du Covars ne tranchent pas sur le masque obligatoire	19 décembre 2022
Le Point	Triple épidémie : le Covars ne se prononce pas sur le masque obligatoire	
Les Echos	Covid : les scientifiques bottent en touche sur l'obligation de port du masque	
L'Humanité	Port du masque : le ni oui ni non du COVARS	
La Croix	Covid, grippe et bronchiolite : pourquoi le Covars peine-t-il à convaincre ?	22 décembre 2022
Futur des vaccins ARNm		
BFMTV	Nobel de médecine: la présidente du Covars se réjouit d'un prix qui tombe "à point nommé"	2 octobre 2023
Challenges	Moderna, L'ARN messenger au service de la santé publique	10 novembre 2023
Libération	Vaccins à ARN messenger : un futur plein de promesses, selon le Covars	
Les Echos	Vaccins à ARNm : en retard, la France se cherche une stratégie	14 février 2023
Marianne	Brigitte Autran : "Investir dans les vaccins à ARN est indispensable à notre autonomie sanitaire"	
Influenza		
Le Monde	Grippe aviaire : les experts du Covars recommandent la vaccination des volailles « dès que possible »	
Les Echos	Grippe aviaire : les autorités se méfient d'une propagation chez l'Homme	13 juin 2023
Le Figaro	Grippe aviaire : la France doit mieux se préparer à un risque croissant	
France Info	Grippe aviaire : "La situation sera inquiétante si les porcs sont contaminés" rassure le Comité de veille et d'anticipation des risques sanitaires	
France Bleu	Transmission de la grippe aviaire à l'homme : l'OMS s'alarme, des spécialistes tempèrent	18 avril 2024
Futura Science	L'évolution rapide de la grippe aviaire fait craindre une « pandémie sévère »	19 avril 24
Le Monde	Grippe aviaire : la propagation mondiale du virus attise les craintes d'une contamination humaine	20 avril 24
20 minutes	Faut-il s'inquiéter des traces de grippe aviaire trouvées dans le lait ?	24 avril 24
Le Point	Vaches américaines contaminées par la grippe aviaire : faut-il s'inquiéter ?	25 avril 2024
Europe 1	Grippe aviaire : pourquoi le cochon est au centre des attentions, selon la présidente du Covars	
BFMTV	"Le vrai risque, c'est vraiment le porc": la présidente du Covars se veut rassurante sur l'épidémie de grippe aviaire	10 mai 2024
Radio France	Grippe aviaire : faut-il avoir la chair de poule ?	
France Info	Grippe aviaire : "Le risque pandémique est réel", affirme le virologue Bruno Lina après l'achat par l'UE de 665 000 doses d'un vaccin	13 juin 2024
Radio France	Grippe aviaire : le risque pandémique "n'est pas majeur, mais il est réel", prévient le virologue Bruno Lina	16 juin 24
Covid-Long		
Europe 1	Covid long : une prise en charge «insatisfaisante» en France, selon le Covars	

Le Monde	Covid-long : un parcours de soins chaotique	
L'Express	Covid Long : "Arrêtons de dire aux patients que c'est dans leur tête, soignons-les !"	
France Info	Covid long : la prise en charge est "insatisfaisante" en France, selon un avis rendu au gouvernement	
Libération	En France, « plusieurs centaines de milliers de personnes » toujours touchées par le Covid-Long	
Les Echos	Covid long : une prise en charge « insatisfaisante » en France	8 novembre 2023
BFMTV	Le COVARS juge la prise en charge du Covid-long « insatisfaisante » en France	
La Croix	Covid long: une prise en charge "insatisfaisante" en France, selon le Covars	
20 minutes	Le Covid long affecte « plusieurs centaines de milliers » de personnes en France	
Nouvel Obs	La prise en charge du Covid long reste « insatisfaisante » en France, affirme le Covars	
Europe 1	Covid long : comment améliorer la prise en charge des patients, jugée insuffisante par le Covars ?	
Figaro	Covid long: causes, symptômes, traitements... Tout ce que nous savons aujourd'hui	9 novembre 2023
C à vous	Le Covid long, un fléau mal reconnu et mal soigné : décryptage dans l'édito de #PatrickCohen	
Libération	La reconnaissance du Covid long par le Covars, une heureuse surprise face au déni du gouvernement	19 novembre 2023
Maladies à transmission vectorielle		
France Inter	Moustique tigre : vers une "augmentation des cas" de dengue, Zika et chikungunya en France, prévient le Covars	
Libération	Climat : la France pourrait connaître des flambées de dengue, Zika et chikungunya «au cours des prochains étés»	
TF1 info	Alerte sur une hausse des cas de dengue, Zika et chikungunya dans les années à venir en France	5 avril 2023
France Info	Dengue, Zika et chikungunya : avec le réchauffement climatique, "l'Hexagone a beaucoup à apprendre des territoires ultramarins"	
Europe 1	Dengue, Zika et chikungunya : pourquoi le nombre de cas va augmenter en France	
20 minutes	Moustique tigre : Pourquoi la France risque-t-elle des épidémies de dengue, zika et chikungunya ?	7 avril 2023
Capital	Epidémie de dengue : voici les solutions efficaces pour vous protéger des moustiques tigres	24 avril 2024
Cartographie des risques de situation sanitaire exceptionnelle		
BFMTV	Infections respiratoires, "maladie X": le Covars fait le point sur les prochaines grandes menaces sanitaires	
L'Express	Ces cataclysmes sanitaires qui nous guettent : "Les infections et la pollution, un cocktail explosif"	10 avril 2024
Le Bien Public	Maladies infectieuses : comment faire face aux nouvelles menaces	
Public Sénat	Epidémie et changement climatique : l'avis des scientifiques	
Capital	Maladie X, Covid, grippe aviaire... elles pourraient vous pourrir la vie les 5 prochaines années	11 avril 2024
Public Sénat	Dengue, virus du Nil, maladie X... Trois ans après le covid, ces nouvelles pandémies qui menacent la France	12 avril 2024
RTL	Grippe aviaire, nouveau coronavirus, "maladie X" : les épidémies qui menacent la France	13 avril 2024
Notre Temps	"Les maladies passant de l'animal à l'homme, principal risque pour la santé dans le futur"	15 avril 2024
BFM TV	Menace numéro 1 : Des scientifiques affirment que la prochaine pandémie sera une grippe	20 avril 2024
Le Point	Santé : la prochaine pandémie sera une grippe, selon une enquête internationale	20 avril 2024

Choléra à Mayotte		
Notre temps	Choléra à Mayotte: une situation "pas défendable", regrette le Covars	4 avril 2024
L'Express	Le choléra, cette menace oubliée qui se rapproche du sol français	19 avril 2024
L'Express	Choléra à Mayotte : nos révélations sur l’origine de l’épidémie	27 mai 2024
Note à l’occasion des élections législatives		
Le Monde	Législatives 2024 : revivez le dernier débat avant le premier tour ; des manifestations contre le RN et l’extrême droite dans plusieurs grandes villes de France	27 juin 2024
Les Echos	Législatives 2024 : les experts en santé publique alertent sur une suppression de l'aide médicale d'Etat	28 juin 2024
France Info	Législatives 2024 : La dangereuse suppression de l’Aide médicale d’État	1 juillet 2024

Appendix 11: COVARS' main recommendations on arboviroses and HPAI

	-April 3, 2023 advice on Dengue, Zika and Chikungunya (link) - Background note on health risks linked to West-Nile and Usutu viruses 20/10/23	-Advice of June 8, 2023 on the avian influenza health risk linked to highly pathogenic avian influenza (link)
Anticipate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Decree no. 2019-258 of March 29, 2019 on the prevention of vector-borne diseases including viruses transmitted by Aedes and Culex : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Assess the positive and negative implications ▪ Developing it in France and overseas - Integrating arboviroses into the national pandemic plan - Sociobehavioral observation tools for arboviroses in crisis situations: preparing for inter-crisis situations 	<p>Integrate the effects of climate change on influenza risk by :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - developing tools to accurately track the evolution of bird migration routes - opening a multi-stakeholder discussion on the economic and health impact of intensive poultry farming
Prevention and vaccination	<p>Adapt the current system for donating blood, organs or tissues to a situation where the number of cases is on the rise by facilitating the interconnection of operators to an updated national and international monitoring database</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Research alternatives to sheltering birds and preventive culling - Improve euthanasia conditions - Evaluate the effects of reactive ring vaccination around an outbreak as soon as it is confirmed, or check the immunity of vaccinated animals
Watch	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Extending the molecular diagnostics network for WNV infection and the dengue-Chik-Zika triad to university hospitals - Set up : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • an information system integrating national and international human, animal and environmental data for all arboviroses, under the aegis of SpF • an expertise structure for zoonotic arboviroses • a single, easy-to-read system for detecting and reporting symptomatic cases of WNV infection, which can then be used for other zoonotic arboviroses - Ensure that WNV screening methods are adapted to a rapidly changing epidemiological context for blood, organ, cell and tissue donations. - Improve the SI-LAV application and enable ARS and mosquito control operators to enter information in the field and produce maps in real time. -Regular monitoring of insecticide resistance in Aedes and Culex vectors of arboviruses 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Active environmental monitoring: Strengthen dedicated resources and integrate DNA environmental monitoring in a sustainable manner. - Passive wildlife surveillance: Support and strengthen dedicated financial and human resources (SAGIR network) and clarify the surveillance responsibilities of the OFB and the DDPP. - Closely involve the MSP in the national animal health epidemio-surveillance platform, and in particular its VSI (Veille Sanitaire Internationale) group dealing with HPAI monitoring.

	<p>Strengthen international surveillance, in particular by creating within SPF a department dedicated to the international surveillance of infectious diseases, in real time and in liaison with the national health watch and the international watch of the animal health epidemiology-surveillance platform (DGAL's ESA platform); include interfaces with business software (transfusion, transplantation, travel medicine, emergencies, etc.) enabling real-time, automated processing.</p>	
<p><i>Diagnose and manage</i></p>	<p>- Adapt healthcare professionals' business software to encourage vigilance and provide information on diagnostic management.</p>	<p>Enable human respiratory samples to be taken in and around contaminated farms (by self-sampling or by veterinarians), followed by screening and diagnostic confirmation of human infection by veterinary laboratories.</p>
<p><i>Manage</i></p>	<p>Vector control : - Set up a national inter-professional technical center with vector control operators and regional working groups - Anti-Culex vector control actions: Establish clear technical recommendations to frame them on an objective scientific basis - quality approach for vector control operators: better formalization and framework for evaluation (indicators of effectiveness and ecological and societal impact) - Specify the conditions of use of biocides and alternative strategies: TIS, Wolbachia, traps, silicone films, , etc.</p>	<p>- Decomartmentalize surveillance, diagnosis and management at the animal/human interface by creating a network of local and national players, - Establish active collaboration between medical and veterinary health authorities (sharing tools, information and resources). - Strengthen standardization of crisis management and coordination between national and local levels by creating an interministerial task force for avian flu</p>
<p><i>Training-Informing-raising awareness among professionals</i></p>	<p>- Improve the level of preparation and information, particularly in mainland France, for the players concerned, by preparing an interministerial training and information plan under the aegis of the MSP for local authorities, healthcare professionals in mainland France, urban planners and building professionals, and associations involved in health/environment. - Update the 2016 CNEV guide for local authorities, including Culex, West Nile and Usutu, and distribute it widely.</p>	<p>-Conduct campaigns and define targeted communication tools, particularly in high-risk areas and for people exposed to avian risk, in times of crisis and between crises, to encourage participatory surveillance and raise awareness of clinical signs. - Reinforce human and financial resources for active surveillance of human infections</p>
<p><i>Mobilizing the general public and preventing societal impacts</i></p>	<p>- Encourage citizen participation (Web site "signalement moustique") encourage the adoption by citizens of behaviors adapted to the fight against the proliferation of vectors through the support of institutional and citizen actions. - Better regulation of marketing messages for repellent or soothing products, to ensure compliance with scientific data and government recommendations.</p>	<p>- Encourage participatory surveillance by pointing out the steps and precautions to be taken in the presence of a dead bird, and by mobilizing farmers, hunters and members of birdwatching associations, in areas where wild birds frequent. -Develop psychological and social support measures for affected breeders, and help restock farms by speeding up compensation payments.</p>

	<p>Educate children from an early age about the concept of risk reduction by including examples of French vector-borne diseases in school life science curricula in the regions concerned.</p>	
<p><i>Evaluate</i></p>	<p>- Have ANSES and expert researchers develop indicators of the entomological and epidemiological effectiveness and the ecological and societal impact of vector control actions.</p> <p>-Evaluate, document and publish the effectiveness of different insecticide treatments and interventions (case-control studies).</p>	<p>-Have a committee of experts evaluate the priority treatments best suited to the various patient groups, and identify an optimal approach to stock composition.</p>
<p><i>Strengthening research</i></p>	<p>- Support :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ specific research programs in epidemiology, medicine, the environment and the human and social sciences. ▪ Development of new biocides with low environmental impact, and ▪ monitoring resistance in mosquitoes 	<p>- Ease regulations in protected areas to allow avian flu research in these zones</p>
	<p>- Ensure the availability of "flash funds" to enable the immediate initiation of research initiatives in the event of an epidemiological event, and the renewal of multi-year funding programs.</p> <p>-Fund long-term, multidisciplinary research that is not conditional on one-off crises and is part of a One Health concept.</p> <p>- Anticipate regulatory obstacles to MOTs between crises and during health crises.</p> <p>- Developing a research institute on human studies dedicated to health risks</p>	